

Path Integral Formulation of Quantum Mechanics

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I affirm that I have identified all my sources and that no part of my dissertation paper uses unacknowledged materials.

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ABSTRACT

In this project report, we present a rigorous introduction to Feynman's path integral formulation of quantum mechanics. We start by outlining the motivation behind the path integral formulation of quantum mechanics. Then we build the mathematics required for defining the sum-over-paths and derive the free particle propagator as well as the propagator for a particle with a non-zero potential energy, with particular focus on linear and quadratic potential energies. We use these results to arrive at some standard results in quantum physics using path integrals: namely Planck-Einstein equation, de-Broglie equation and Schrödinger equation. This helps us appreciate the equivalence between the path integral and the canonical formulation, as well as understand the difference in the approaches employed by the two to arrive at the results. We also use Python to generate plots of the free particle wave function and propagator as functions of position and time, and explore the conceptual difference between the wave function in canonical quantum mechanics and the propagator used in the path integral formulation. We also look at the application of the free particle propagator in describing a particle that moves between two potential-free points in spacetime, but via an intermediate point with a non-zero potential, in one of the appendices. In the end, we discuss path integrals in a broad perspective, and make some general comments on the future of theoretical physics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Quantum mechanics is a theory of possibilities and probabilities. It provides us with a mathematical framework to predict the possible outcomes a measurement on a quantum system can yield, and calculate the probabilities of each possible outcome. It was developed in an attempt to address some contradictions between theory and experiment, the resolution of which demanded major modifications in the existing theories for describing Nature.

In the early twentieth century, making extensive use of linear algebra, Erwin Schrödinger reduced the problem of finding the possibilities and probabilities of a measurement in quantum mechanics to a well-defined mathematical exercise of finding eigenvalues and the corresponding eigenvectors of the associated Hermitian operator. One of the most important questions in quantum mechanics revolves around the time evolution of the initial state of a system. The Schrödinger equation determines how a system with initial state $|\psi(t_0)\rangle$ evolves with time. Schrödinger equation in one-dimension is written as:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\psi(t)\rangle = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + V \right] |\psi(t)\rangle$$

Here, \hbar is the reduced Planck's constant, named after Max Planck, m is the mass of the system, V is the potential. The quantity $\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + V \right]$ is the Hamiltonian of the system, which determines the dynamics of the system. Schrödinger's formulation of quantum mechanics builds on the Hamiltonian formulation in classical mechanics.

The Lagrangian formulation in classical mechanics is an alternative formulation that studies the dynamics of a classical system. The time-evolution of the system is determined by Lagrange's equation of motion. The Lagrangian of the system L is defined as:

$$L = T - V$$

where T and V are the kinetic and potential energies of the system. The classical action S is defined as:

$$S = \int_{t_0}^t L dt$$

Here, we are studying the evolution of the system between time t_0 and time t . This action describes the trajectory of the particle in evolving from the initial state to the final state. Classically, there is only a single trajectory – the one for which the action S is minimum. Classical systems always evolve along the path that minimizes the action. This path is called the classical path.

Just like Schrödinger formulated quantum mechanics based on the Hamiltonian, one might ask whether it is possible to create an alternate formulation of quantum mechanics based on the Lagrangian. Perhaps this formed the basis of Paul Dirac's comment on the possible connection between classical action and quantum mechanics, which inspired Richard Feynman to develop the path integral formulation of quantum mechanics.

Although path integrals offer no significant advantage over the usual canonical formulation of quantum mechanics for single-particle systems, the path integral formulation reigns superior in field theories. Path integrals are extremely useful in complicated situations in quantum field theory, which is a

reconciliation of quantum mechanics and the special theory of relativity. Quantum field theory serves as the mathematical structure on which much of theoretical high energy physics is based. Path integrals are also referred to as one of the most important generalizations in physics, owing, in large part, to its mathematical elegance.

Let us now focus on a particle that moves from some initial point **a** with coordinates (x_a, t_a) to some fixed final point **b** with coordinates (x_b, t_b) in spacetime. This can be achieved via many paths, as long as the initial and final states are **a** and **b**. Feynman stated that the probability amplitude $\langle b(x_b, t_b) | a(x_a, t_a) \rangle$ is expressed as:

$$K(x_b, t_b; x_a, t_a) = A e^{iS/\hbar}$$

Here, $K(x_b, t_b; x_a, t_a)$ is referred to as the Kernel or the propagator. It is essentially the probability amplitude $\langle b(x_b, t_b) | a(x_a, t_a) \rangle$, and can also simply be written $K(b, a)$. In the right-hand side, S is the classical action of the particle, and the constant factor A ensures that the Kernel is normalized. The actual probability of the event $a \rightarrow b$ is given by the square of the modulus of the Kernel.

Unlike in classical mechanics, here the particle can evolve from the initial state **a** to the final state **b** via many different paths. It is impossible to assign a fixed trajectory to the evolution of the particle. The path corresponding to the classical action is called the “classical path,” as determined by the principle of least action. As we will see, in the classical limit, all the paths except the classical path cancel out. However, at scales where we cannot make classical approximations and have to rely solely on quantum mechanics, we have to take into consideration all the paths. The particle can evolve through any path between fixed initial and final states (including the classical path) with a non-zero probability. Each path contributes to the total propagator. We calculate the action S for all the possible paths (S_0, S_1, S_2, \dots), and add the corresponding probability amplitudes for all the paths to calculate the total propagator.

$$K(b, a) \sim e^{iS_0/\hbar} + e^{iS_1/\hbar} + e^{iS_2/\hbar} + e^{iS_3/\hbar} + \dots$$

The Kernel $K(b, a)$ can be thought of as the total probability amplitude of the event $a \rightarrow b$ (the time evolution of the particle from state **a** to state **b**), and is obtained by summing over the probability amplitudes for all the possible paths (with actions S_0, S_1, S_2, \dots) between **a** and **b**. The probability of the event $a \rightarrow b$ is given by the square of the modulus of the Kernel.

Figure 1: The classical path from $a(x_a, t_a)$ to $b(x_b, t_b)$, according to classical mechanics. (Source: Path Integral Approach to Single-Particle Motion in Forced Harmonic Potential by Pimpimon Khumwong.)

Figure 2: Different possible paths from $a(x_a, t_a)$ to $b(x_b, t_b)$, according to quantum mechanics. (Source: Path Integral Approach to Single-Particle Motion in Forced Harmonic Potential by Pimpimon Khumwong.)

We will now look at the double-slit experiment (using electrons) to illustrate the possibility of alternate trajectories (in addition to the classical path) of the evolution of a quantum system from a fixed initial state to a fixed final state. This experiment is a slightly modified version of Young's double-slit experiment; the major difference being here we will replace the light source in Young's original double-slit experiment with an electron source, with electrons being fired at the screen with the two slits. The experimental setup is shown below. Some of the electrons that are fired will pass through the slits and hit the final screen. By keeping track of the different positions on the final screen hit by the electrons, we can determine the intensity of the electrons on the final screen (after a sufficiently large number of electrons have been fired at the double-slit).

Figure 3: Experimental set-up of the double-slit experiment with electrons. (Source: Wikipedia.)

Classically, we would expect that the most probable location for finding the electrons on the final screen to be the areas on the screen directly behind the two slits. Since some electrons may get deflected through an angle at the slits, we might find a few electrons at other positions as well; but the maximum intensity of electrons would be directly behind the two slits, as illustrated below.

Figure 4: Expected electron intensity on the final screen in the double-slit experiment. (Source: *Intelligence, The Foundation of Matter* by Albert Hoffmann, HAL Open Science.)

But in reality, we obtain a pattern which is similar to the interference pattern observed with light in Young's double-slit experiment, as shown below (Figure 5). The maximum number of electrons can be found in the region on the final screen that corresponds to the region between the two slits on the slit screen (the central maxima). Along both sides of the central maxima, there are alternate maxima (regions where we can find the electrons) and minima (regions where there are no electrons).

The region of the central maxima is not accessible to most of the electrons in the classical picture. The results of this experiment, thus, defy a classical explanation. We get some hint that in addition to the classical paths, there are other possible paths contributing to the overall electron intensity on the final screen. This serves as a good illustration of the notion of alternate paths of evolution of quantum particles (in this case, electrons).

Figure 5: Observed electron intensity on the final screen in the double-slit experiment. (Source: *Intelligence, The Foundation of Matter* by Albert Hoffmann, HAL Open Science.)

Figure 6: P_1 represents the probability distribution of electrons on the final screen when only slit 1 is kept open (slit 2 is closed). P_2 represents the same when only slit 2 is kept open. P_{12} is the probability distribution when both the slits are open. (Source: *Foundations of Science*. DOI: 10.1007/s10699-018-9557-z)

If we keep only one slit open in the above experiment, then we get the greatest number of electrons directly behind the open slit, as illustrated in the figure above. If we keep the slit 1 open and slit 2 closed, the corresponding intensity distribution is P_1 ; if we keep only slit 2 open, then the corresponding intensity distribution is P_2 . Mathematically, P_1 is the square of modulus of the amplitude for the case when only slit 1 is open, say $|\psi_1|^2$. Similarly, $P_2 = |\psi_2|^2$, where ψ_2 is the amplitude for the case when only slit 2 is open. Now, if we keep both the slits open, the resulting intensity distribution P_{12} is not the sum of P_1 and P_2 , as we would have expected classically. Rather, to calculate P_{12} , we first sum up the corresponding amplitudes and then square the modulus of this sum. This is the superposition principle, where we first sum up the amplitudes for all the possible paths joining the initial and final states, and then square the modulus of the sum of amplitudes to obtain the total probability of the system evolving to the final state from the initial state.

$$P_{12} = |\psi_{12}|^2 = |\psi_1 + \psi_2|^2$$

The superposition principle in quantum mechanics is analogous to the superposition principle in classical wave theory. For waves in classical physics, the superposition principle essentially governs the interference of the waves. It states that the amplitude (or displacement) of the resulting wave when many waves interfere is the sum of the amplitudes (or displacements) of the individual waves. In quantum mechanics, we replace “amplitude” or “displacement” with “probability amplitude”. Probability amplitudes in quantum mechanics obey the superposition principle as long as there is no real measurement being made on the system when it is at an intermediate state between the initial and final states. Otherwise, the interference is destroyed and superposition principle no longer holds. In such cases, the total probability is simply the sum of the individual probabilities. For instance, when we are keeping only one slit open in the double-slit experiment, the interference is destroyed. In this case, the resultant intensity distribution, say P , is given by:

$$P = P_1 + P_2 = |\psi_1|^2 + |\psi_2|^2$$

In the double-slit experiment, if we want to detect which slit an electron went through, we have to make a physical measurement on the electron between the initial state (when it is in the electron gun) and the final state (when it has reached the final screen). For instance, we can put detectors in front of

the slits. If we do that, the interference pattern on the final screen vanishes, because superposition principle no longer holds.

In the following sections, we will build up the mathematics of the path integral formulation, study the propagator for a free particle and use it to derive some familiar results of quantum mechanics, like de Broglie's relation and the Planck-Einstein relation. Then we will arrive at Schrödinger equation and study the quantum harmonic oscillator using path integrals.

2. THE PATH INTEGRAL FORMULATION OF QUANTUM MECHANICS

In this section, we will see how the Kernel is defined in the path integral formulation. Then, we will discuss the significance of the classical path, and why in the classical limit the other paths become insignificant. Then we will see how the sum over paths is defined mathematically. Finally, we will derive the multiplicative law of propagators and compare with the superposition principle in quantum mechanics.

2.1 The Kernel

As we have discussed, a particle can move from an initial point \mathbf{a} in spacetime to a final point \mathbf{b} via many paths. Each path contributes to the Kernel with different phases. The contribution of each path has a phase proportional to the corresponding action S for that path, and is given by:

$$C \sim e^{iS/\hbar}$$

The phase is actually S/\hbar , i.e., the action S for the corresponding path in units of the reduced Planck constant \hbar . The action S is defined as the time integral of the Lagrangian of the path, and further, the Lagrangian is defined as the difference of the kinetic and potential energies of the system. Thus, clearly the action S depends on position, velocity and time, and is different for different paths.

The Kernel $K(b, a)$ is the sum of the contributions from all the paths from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} . Let us label the paths between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} as 0, 1, 2, 3, ... ('0' corresponds to the classical path) and the corresponding actions as $S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3 \dots$. Then the Kernel is given by:

$$K(b, a) \sim e^{iS_0/\hbar} + e^{iS_1/\hbar} + e^{iS_2/\hbar} + e^{iS_3/\hbar} + \dots$$

As we have discussed, the Kernel corresponds to the total probability amplitude of the particle moving from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} . The corresponding probability is given by the square of the modulus of the Kernel:

$$P_{a \rightarrow b} = |K(b, a)|^2$$

We have to multiply the expression for the Kernel with a normalization constant, say A , to ensure that the normalization condition is satisfied. Thus, we can now write:

$$K(b, a) = A(e^{iS_0/\hbar} + e^{iS_1/\hbar} + e^{iS_2/\hbar} + e^{iS_3/\hbar} + \dots) = A \sum_{j=0,1,\dots} e^{iS_j/\hbar}$$

Any physical system must satisfy the normalization condition, which states that the probability of finding the particle at some point in all of spacetime must be 1. This is obvious, since the particle must end up at some point within spacetime. Normalizing the Kernel is essential if it is to be treated as the probability amplitude corresponding to a physical event.

2.2 The Classical Path

The classical path (between given initial and final points) is the path corresponding to the classical action, usually denoted by S_0 :

$$S_0 = \int_{t_0}^t L dt = \int_{t_0}^t (T - V) dt$$

Here, T and V represent the kinetic and potential energies, respectively; and the corresponding path is referred to as the “classical path”.

Of all the paths joining the initial and final points in the path integral formulation, the classical path and those differing slightly from it have the maximum contribution to the corresponding Kernel.

Let us look at the expression for the Kernel:

$$K(b, a) \sim e^{iS_0/\hbar} + e^{iS_1/\hbar} + e^{iS_2/\hbar} + e^{iS_3/\hbar} + \dots$$

Each $e^{iS_j/\hbar}$, $j = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots$ can be represented by a vector on the complex plane, i.e., arrows making angles S_j/\hbar with the horizontal axis (the real number line). Thus, the sum of the contributions of all the paths can be qualitatively understood as the sum of the vectors.

When the angle S_j/\hbar varies widely from one path to the next, the net displacement between the tail of the first vector and the tip of the final vector is usually very small, as outlined in the figure below.

Figure 7: The vector OA makes an angle θ_1 with the horizontal axis. The next vector AB makes an angle θ_2 with the horizontal axis, which is significantly different from θ_1 . The next vectors BC , CD and DE make angles θ_3 , θ_4 and θ_5 with the horizontal axis respectively. The resultant displacement OE is not very large. (Generated using Paint.)

In context of path integrals, this translates to the contribution of paths with significantly-varying phases to be very small.

Next, let us consider the case when the angle S_j/\hbar does not change much from one path to the next. In this case, the net displacement between the tail of the first vector and the tip of the final vector is large, as outlined in the figure below.

Figure 8: The vector OA makes an angle θ_1 with the horizontal axis. The next vector AB makes an angle θ_2 with the horizontal axis, which is only slightly different from θ_1 . The next vector BC makes an angle θ_3 with the horizontal axis, which is again not very different from the previous angles. The resultant displacement OC is very large. (Generated using Paint.)

The second case corresponds to the paths that vary only slightly from the classical path S_0 . The classical path and these paths (that do not vary much from the classical path) contribute maximally to the Kernel.

As we have seen, the contribution C of each path has a phase proportional to the corresponding action S for that path.

$$C \sim e^{iS/\hbar}$$

Using Euler's identity $e^{ix} = \cos(x) + i \sin(x)$, we can write:

$$C \sim \cos(S/\hbar) + i \sin(S/\hbar)$$

The classical limit corresponds to the condition $S \gg \hbar$. This means the action S is very large compared to \hbar , and as a result the phase S/\hbar is extremely large. If we move a path with action $S \gg \hbar$ by a very small amount, the change in S would also be vanishingly small in the classical scale. However, in the quantum scale (in units of \hbar), even a small change in S leads to a significant change in the corresponding path.

To illustrate this, consider two arbitrary values 1000 and 1001. In the classical scale, the difference between 1001 and 1000 is 1, which is not a very large value. However, if we divide these values by an extremely small number, say 0.000000001, and then calculate the difference between these two new values, we would get a very large value.

Thus, a small change in S corresponds to a significant change in the phase S/\hbar , \hbar being a very small number. This means the sinusoidal waves $\cos(S/\hbar)$ and $\sin(S/\hbar)$ vary rapidly between positive and negative values, producing a net contribution of zero in the classical limit ($S \gg \hbar$). If one path makes

a positive contribution, then another path that is infinitesimally close to this path (in the classical scale) will make an equal but negative contribution to the total sum over paths.

Since the classical action S_0 is the minimum action, a small change in the classical path does not give rise to any change in S_0 ; since S_0 is a minima, its first order derivative $dS_0 = 0$. Thus, we get a non-zero net contribution only for the classical path. So, in the classical limit, the classical path is the only path that contributes to the Kernel. The other paths can be ignored in the classical limit, and therefore quantum mechanics reproduces the same results of classical mechanics. However, when S is not sufficiently large, we cannot neglect the other paths. At quantum scales, the other paths also contribute to the Kernel.

2.3 Constructing the Sum

Let us start with a particle moving from point **a** (t_a, x_a) to point **b** (t_b, x_b) in spacetime. As we have discussed, there are many possible paths via which the particle can reach **b** from **a**. The points **a** and **b**, and all the paths can be outlined on a two-dimensional space, where we plot position along one axis and time along the other axis.

First, we choose a subset of the set of all the paths. In order to do this, we divide the independent variable time into discrete parts of equal width, say ε . This yields a set of values of time t_i between the initial and final time values t_a and t_b , with an interval of size ε between one another. Mathematically, $\varepsilon = t_{i+1} - t_i$. Let us assume there are N time steps. In other words, i runs from 0 to N . Thus, $t_a = t_0, t_b = t_N$, and similarly let us define $x_a = x_0, x_b = x_N$. Clearly, $N\varepsilon = t_b - t_a = t_N - t_0$. At each t_i , we choose some x_i in the x -versus- t space. In this way, we construct a path by connecting with straight lines all the x_i s selected for every t_i (Figure 9).

We can define a sum over all the paths constructed in this manner by evaluating a multiple integral over all values of x_i , for i between 1 and $N - 1$. Since 0 and N – the initial and final points – are fixed, we do not include these points in the multiple integral.

The resulting sum over paths (or the Kernel) can thus be expressed as:

$$K(b, a) \sim \int \dots \iiint \phi[x(t)] dx_1 dx_2 \dots dx_{N-1}$$

where $\phi[x(t)] = e^{iS[b,a]/\hbar}$ is the contribution of the corresponding path. To obtain a more accurate sum, we take the limit of the above expression as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. This makes the interval between the time steps infinitesimally small. We also multiply the above expression by a normalizing factor $(1/A)^N$. This gives us:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N \int \dots \iiint e^{iS[b,a]/\hbar} dx_1 dx_2 \dots dx_{N-1}$$

Since there are $N - 1$ integrals and N ‘ $(1/A)$ ’s, we can rewrite the above expression as:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{A} \int \dots \iiint e^{iS[b,a]/\hbar} \frac{dx_1}{A} \frac{dx_2}{A} \dots \frac{dx_{N-1}}{A}$$

Previously, we defined the Kernel as the sum of the contributions of all the paths. Now, we define it as an integral. Ideally, the limits of each of the above integrals are from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$.

Introducing compact notations, we can write the above expression in a simpler way:

$$K(b, a) = \int_a^b e^{\frac{iS[b,a]}{\hbar}} \mathcal{D}x(t)$$

This is the general notation of the path integral between **a** and **b**.

Figure 9: One constructed path between **a** and **b** has been shown in this figure. This path has been constructed by joining the x_i s at every time step t_i with straight lines. (Source: *Quantum Mechanics and Path Integrals* by Richard Feynman, Albert Hibbs and Daniel Styer.)

2.4 The Multiplicative Law of Propagators

Let us now introduce a new point in spacetime, **c**, between the initial and final points **a** and **b**. The time value corresponding to the point **c** is t_c , and the position corresponding to **c** is x_c . Instead of looking at all the paths between **a** and **b**, now we will first look at all the paths between **a** and **c**, and then all the paths between **c** and **b**.

Figure 10: All the paths from **a** to **b** that pass through an intermediate spacetime point **c**. (Source: *Path Integral Approach to Single-Particle Motion in Forced Harmonic Potential* by Pimpimon Khumwong.)

We defined the Kernel for the particle to move from **a** to **b** to be $K(b, a)$. In the same way, the Kernel $K(c, a)$ is for the particle to move from **a** to **c**, and the Kernel $K(b, c)$ is for the particle to move from **c** to **b**.

The x_i s between $x_a \equiv x_0$ and $x_b \equiv x_N$ are:

$$x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{c-1}, x_c, x_{c+1}, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N$$

For a free particle, the potential energy $V = 0$. Thus, the Lagrangian would just be the kinetic energy $T = mv^2/2$, where v is the velocity of the particle. The velocity of the particle for a single step i to $i + 1$ is given by the corresponding displacement $(x_{i+1} - x_i)$ divided by the corresponding time interval $t_{i+1} - t_i = \varepsilon$. Thus, the net action S from **a** to **b**, for a free particle, is given by:

$$S = \left\{ \frac{m(x_1 - x_a)^2}{2\varepsilon} + \dots + \frac{m(x_c - x_{c-1})^2}{2\varepsilon} \right\} + \dots + \left\{ \frac{m(x_{c+1} - x_c)^2}{2\varepsilon} + \dots + \frac{m(x_b - x_{N-1})^2}{2\varepsilon} \right\}$$

Let us group the terms and denote the portion within the first set of curly braces by $S(c, a)$ and the terms in the second set of curly braces by $S(b, c)$. This gives:

$$S = S(c, a) + S(b, c)$$

So:

$$e^{iS/\hbar} = e^{i/\hbar[S(c,a)+S(b,c)]} = e^{iS(c,a)/\hbar} e^{iS(b,c)/\hbar}$$

Substituting this expression in the Kernel $K(b, a)$, we get:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{A} \int \dots \iiint e^{iS(c,a)/\hbar} e^{iS(b,c)/\hbar} \frac{dx_1}{A} \frac{dx_2}{A} \dots \frac{dx_{N-1}}{A}$$

We can rewrite the above expression in the following way:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{A} \int \frac{dx_{N-1}}{A} \dots \int \frac{dx_{c+1}}{A} \int \frac{dx_c}{A} \int \frac{dx_{c-1}}{A} \dots \int \frac{dx_2}{A} \int \frac{dx_1}{A} e^{iS(c,a)/\hbar} e^{iS(b,c)/\hbar}$$

Rearranging the above expression once more, we get:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{1}{A} \int \frac{dx_{N-1}}{A} \dots \int \frac{dx_{c+1}}{A} e^{iS(b,c)/\hbar} \right) \int dx_c \left(\frac{1}{A} \int \frac{dx_{c-1}}{A} \dots \int \frac{dx_2}{A} \int \frac{dx_1}{A} e^{iS(c,a)/\hbar} \right)$$

Now, using the general definition of the Kernel:

$$K(Y, X) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{A} \int \frac{dx_{N-1}}{A} \int \frac{dx_{N-2}}{A} \dots \int \frac{dx_2}{A} \int \frac{dx_1}{A} e^{iS(Y,X)/\hbar}$$

we can write:

$$K(b, a) = \int dx_c K(b, c) K(c, a)$$

This is known as the multiplicative law of propagators (the terms “Kernel” and “propagator” can be used interchangeably). All we have done is break the original journey from **a** to **b** into two parts – from **a** to **c** and then from **c** to **b**. First, we fix the intermediate point **c** and sum over all paths from **a** to **c**, given by the Kernel $K(c, a)$, and then sum over all paths from **c** to **b**, given by the Kernel $K(b, c)$. Thus, essentially, we split the sum over all paths from **a** to **b** into the sum over all paths from **a** to **c**

and the sum over all paths from \mathbf{c} to \mathbf{b} . Finally, we integrate (limits $-\infty$ to $+\infty$) over x_c to take into account all possible values of the intermediate point \mathbf{c} . This final expression, clearly, is equivalent to the original sum over paths from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} , given by $K(b, a)$.

The above equation is similar to the expression of the superposition principle in quantum mechanics. We have already illustrated the superposition principle using the double-slit experiment with electrons. Mathematically, the superposition principle can be expressed as:

$$\langle b|a \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^n \langle b|c_i \rangle \langle c_i|a \rangle$$

Here, $\langle b|a \rangle$ is the probability amplitude from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} , analogous to $K(b, a)$. In the same way, $\langle b|c_i \rangle$ is the probability amplitude from some \mathbf{c} to \mathbf{b} , and $\langle c_i|a \rangle$ is the probability amplitude from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{c} . We have assumed that there are n number of discrete possible values of \mathbf{c} , and the summation over i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) ensures that we take into account all the possibilities for \mathbf{c} . In continuum notation and in terms of the Kernel, the expression of the superposition principle discussed above becomes:

$$K(b, a) = \int dx_c K(b, c)K(c, a)$$

In the canonical formulation of quantum mechanics, \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{c} in the superposition principle can be interpreted as outcomes of corresponding observables \hat{a} , \hat{b} and \hat{c} . For example, if \hat{a} is the velocity observable for the system under consideration, a measurement on \hat{a} will yield an outcome that corresponds to the velocity of that system. Similarly, if \hat{b} is the position observable for the system under consideration, a measurement on \hat{b} will yield an outcome that corresponds to the position of that system. Suppose we make a measurement on observable \hat{a} and obtain outcome \mathbf{a} . Then on the same system, we perform another measurement on observable \hat{b} and obtain outcome \mathbf{b} . Then $\langle b|a \rangle$ represents the probability amplitude of this event, in which we perform two subsequent measurements of observables \hat{a} and \hat{b} respectively, and obtain outcomes \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} respectively. The observable \hat{c} is an arbitrary observable, a measurement on which can yield one of n possible outcomes: c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n . Here, we are not physically making a measurement on \hat{c} . We can mathematically express $\langle b|a \rangle$ in this manner. We notice that it seems like we are considering the path from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} via all possible values of \mathbf{c} . We essentially did the same thing when deriving the expression for the multiplicative law of propagators: we considered an arbitrary intermediate point c in spacetime, between the fixed initial and final points a and b , and finally considered all possibilities for \mathbf{c} .

The corresponding probability of the event $a \rightarrow b$ described above is given by:

$$|\langle b|a \rangle|^2 = \left| \sum_{i=1}^n \langle b|c_i \rangle \langle c_i|a \rangle \right|^2$$

We calculate the square of the modulus of the sum of all the probability amplitudes.

However, if in addition to the measurements on \hat{a} and \hat{b} , we actually make a physical measurement on the intermediate observable \hat{c} , the superposition principle would no longer hold. Then the probability of the event $a \rightarrow b$ would be given by:

$$|\langle b|a \rangle|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n |\langle b|c_i \rangle \langle c_i|a \rangle|^2$$

In this case, the total probability from **a** to **b** is given by the sum of the individual probabilities from **a** to **b** via every possible value of **c**. In context of the double-slit experiment discussed previously, this corresponds to an attempt to make a measurement on the electron when it is between the initial and final screens, in order to determine the slit the electron passed through.

In the next section, we will study the free particle and derive the expression for its Kernel. We will also derive some familiar results for the free particle using the Kernel.

3. THE FREE PARTICLE

In this section, we will look at the free particle. A free particle is not under the influence of any potential field; thus, the potential energy is zero for the free particle. The primary motivation behind studying the free particle is that the calculations for a free particle are relatively simple. Thus, deriving the propagator for the free particle is a good starting point for understanding the path integral formulation of quantum mechanics. In this section, we will also derive some results of standard quantum physics – namely de Broglie equation, Planck equation and Schrödinger equation – using the free particle propagator.

3.1 The Free Particle Action

Since the potential energy V is zero for a free particle, the Lagrangian L is given by:

$$L = T = \frac{mv^2}{2} = \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2$$

where m is the mass of the free particle, and $v = \frac{dx}{dt}$ is its velocity.

Figure 11: The path from a to b , with initial points $(t_a, x_a) \equiv (t_0, x_0)$ and final point $(t_b, x_b) \equiv (t_N, x_N)$, where N is the number of time steps the total time interval has been divided into, the width of each interval being ϵ . (Source: *Variational Principles in Physics* by Jean-Louis Basdevant. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21692-3_9)

From figure 11, we see that between t_0 and t_1 , the corresponding interval along the position axis is $dx = x_1 - x_0$. Thus,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{x_1 - x_0}{t_0 - t_1} = \frac{x_1 - x_0}{\epsilon}$$

Similarly, between t_1 and t_2 , $dx = x_2 - x_1$, and

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{\epsilon}$$

and so on.

The action for the path **a** to **b** is given by:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} L dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 dt$$

Since we are dealing with discrete steps ($dt = \varepsilon$), we can express the action as follows:

$$S = \frac{m}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x_1 - x_0}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x_2 - x_1}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x_3 - x_2}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{x_N - x_{N-1}}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 \right] \varepsilon$$

This is the discretized free particle action.

3.2 The Free Particle Propagator

To derive the expression of the free particle propagator, we start with an extremely simplified version of the above picture: we consider the entire time interval between **a** and **b** to be divided into two equal parts, each of width ε . Thus, there are three points that can be plotted on the two-dimensional spacetime plot in this case: the initial point (t_a, x_a) , the intermediate point, say (t_1, x_1) and the final point (t_b, x_b) . The action in this case is:

$$S = \frac{m}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x_1 - x_a}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x_b - x_1}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 \right] \varepsilon = \frac{m}{2} \left[\frac{(x_1 - x_a)^2 + (x_b - x_1)^2}{\varepsilon} \right]$$

Clearly, the action S is only a function of x_1 , since x_a and x_b are constants. Now, let us evaluate:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1$$

where k is a constant. Using the expression for the action, we get:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon} [(x_1 - x_a)^2 + (x_b - x_1)^2]} dx_1$$

Now, we will use a result of Gaussian integrals (see Appendix 1 for the derivation of this result):

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-k_1(x-a)^2 - k_2(x-b)^2} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{k_1 + k_2}} e^{-\frac{k_1 k_2}{k_1 + k_2} (a-b)^2}$$

Let us put $k_1 = k_2 = \frac{km}{2\varepsilon}$, $a = x_a$, $b = x_b$ and $x = x_1$. Noting that $(x_1 - x_b)^2 = (x_b - x_1)^2$ in the above expression, we get:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\pi\varepsilon}{km}} e^{-\frac{km}{4\varepsilon} (x_a - x_b)^2}$$

The Gaussian function $e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$ is normalized on being multiplied by a normalization constant $\frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}}$

(see Appendix 1). Thus, to normalize $e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon} (x_a - x_b)^2}$, we need a normalization constant $\sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi\varepsilon}} = \frac{1}{A}$ (say).

Now:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}[(x_1-x_a)^2+(x_b-x_1)^2]} dx_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}(x_1-x_a)^2 - \frac{km}{2\varepsilon}(x_b-x_1)^2} dx_1$$

Since we have two terms of the form $-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}(x_1 - x_i)^2$, $i = a, b$, here, the normalization constant for the entire integrand would be $N = \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^2 = \frac{km}{2\pi\varepsilon}$.

Thus, the final normalized expression for $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1$ would be:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1 = \frac{km}{2\pi\varepsilon} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\varepsilon}{km}} e^{-\frac{km}{4\varepsilon}(x_a-x_b)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(2\varepsilon)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(2\varepsilon)}(x_a-x_b)^2}$$

We recall that $2\varepsilon = t_b - t_a$, or $\varepsilon = \frac{t_b-t_a}{2}$, since we began by assuming that the time interval (t_a, t_b) is divided into just two parts of width ε each. Thus, we may write:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1 = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(t_b-t_a)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(t_b-t_a)}(x_a-x_b)^2}$$

Now, let us assume that the time interval (t_a, t_b) is divided into three equal parts of width ε each. This means:

$$\frac{t_b - t_a}{3} = \varepsilon$$

In this case, the action is given by:

$$S = \frac{m}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x_1 - x_a}{\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{x_2 - x_1}{\varepsilon}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{x_b - x_2}{\varepsilon}\right)^2 \right] \varepsilon = \frac{m}{2} \left[\frac{(x_1 - x_a)^2 + (x_2 - x_1)^2 + (x_b - x_2)^2}{\varepsilon} \right]$$

The spacetime points are (t_a, x_a) , (t_1, x_1) , (t_2, x_2) and (t_b, x_b) . Using the same logic as above, clearly the normalization constant in this case would be $\left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3$, where $\frac{1}{A} = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi\varepsilon}}$ as derived previously. We notice that here:

$$e^{-kS} = e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}[(x_1-x_a)^2+(x_2-x_1)^2+(x_b-x_2)^2]}$$

is a product of three Gaussian functions and depends on two variables x_1 and x_2 . Now, we can integrate e^{-kS} as follows (let's denote this integration by I):

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1 dx_2 \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1 dx_2 = \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}[(x_1-x_a)^2+(x_2-x_1)^2+(x_b-x_2)^2]} dx_1 dx_2 \end{aligned}$$

First, we integrate with respect to x_2 , treating x_1 as a constant.

$$\begin{aligned}
I &= \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}(x_1-x_a)^2} dx_1 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}[(x_2-x_1)^2+(x_b-x_2)^2]} dx_2 \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}(x_1-x_a)^2} dx_1 \sqrt{\frac{\pi\varepsilon}{km}} e^{-\frac{km}{4\varepsilon}(x_1-x_b)^2}
\end{aligned}$$

Here, we have once more used the result of Gaussian integrals in the integration over x_2 :

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-k_1(x-a)^2-k_2(x-b)^2} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{k_1+k_2}} e^{-\frac{k_1k_2}{k_1+k_2}(a-b)^2}$$

Thus, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
I &= \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 \sqrt{\frac{\pi\varepsilon}{km}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}(x_1-x_a)^2} e^{-\frac{km}{2(2\varepsilon)}(x_1-x_b)^2} dx_1 \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 \sqrt{\frac{\pi\varepsilon}{km}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}(x_1-x_a)^2 - \frac{km}{2(2\varepsilon)}(x_1-x_b)^2} dx_1
\end{aligned}$$

Using the above result of Gaussian integral once again, this time with $k_1 = \frac{km}{2\varepsilon}$, $k_2 = \frac{km}{2(2\varepsilon)}$, $x = x_1$, $a = x_a$ and $b = x_b$, we get:

$$I = \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 \sqrt{\frac{\pi\varepsilon}{km}} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\varepsilon}{3km}} e^{-\frac{km}{6\varepsilon}(x_a-x_b)^2}$$

Now, using $\left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^3 = \left(\sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi\varepsilon}}\right)^3$ and simplifying the above expression, we obtain:

$$I = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(3\varepsilon)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(3\varepsilon)}(x_b-x_a)^2}$$

Replacing $3\varepsilon = t_b - t_a$ in the above expression, we obtain:

$$I = \iint_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1 dx_2 = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(t_b-t_a)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(t_b-t_a)}(x_b-x_a)^2}$$

This is exactly the same expression we obtained for $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-kS} dx_1$ in the previous case, where we assumed the time interval (t_a, t_b) to be divided into two equal parts. Thus, we see that the final expression of the integral is independent of the number of time steps. If we divide the time interval (t_a, t_b) into N equal parts, each of width ε , then the integration will be over $N - 1$ variables: $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{N-1}$.

The action can be written as the discrete sum ($x_a \equiv x_0$ and $x_b \equiv x_N$):

$$S = \frac{m}{2} \left[\frac{(x_1 - x_0)^2}{\varepsilon} + \frac{(x_2 - x_1)^2}{\varepsilon} + \frac{(x_3 - x_2)^2}{\varepsilon} + \dots + \frac{(x_N - x_{N-1})^2}{\varepsilon} \right] = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_i - x_{i-1})^2}{\varepsilon}$$

For this case, the normalization constant is $\left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N$, and the integration of e^{-kS} can be determined by extrapolating the previously derived expression:

$$I = \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N \int \dots \iiint e^{-kS} dx_1 dx_2 \dots dx_{N-1} = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(N\varepsilon)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(N\varepsilon)}(x_b-x_a)^2}$$

Using $N\varepsilon = t_b - t_a$, we get:

$$I = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(t_b - t_a)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(t_b-t_a)}(x_b-x_a)^2}$$

Now, we will divide the time interval (t_a, t_b) into an infinite number of time steps, each of an infinitesimally small width. This means $N \rightarrow \infty$ or equivalently, $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. The relation $N\varepsilon = t_b - t_a$ would still be valid here, of course. In this case, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N \int \dots \iiint e^{-kS} dx_1 dx_2 \dots dx_{N-1} \\ &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N \int \dots \iiint e^{-\frac{km}{2\varepsilon}[(x_1-x_a)^2 + (x_2-x_1)^2 + \dots + (x_b-x_{N-1})^2]} dx_1 dx_2 \dots dx_{N-1} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(t_b - t_a)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(t_b-t_a)}(x_b-x_a)^2} \end{aligned}$$

In usual notation, using $S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 dt$, we may write:

$$I = \int e^{-k \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 dt} \mathcal{D}x(t) = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(t_b - t_a)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(t_b-t_a)}(x_b-x_a)^2}$$

The left-hand side of the above equation is a sum over paths. A given set of values of $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{N-1}$ defines a path. For each given path, the integrand e^{-kS} assumes a specific value. If we vary the values of $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{N-1}$ in the above integration, the integrand essentially gets evaluated for different paths (hence ‘‘sum over paths’’).

Let us now recall the general form of the Kernel or propagator derived earlier:

$$K(b, a) = \int_a^b e^{\frac{iS[b,a]}{\hbar}} \mathcal{D}x(t)$$

In our calculations for the free particle, we started with an integrand of the form e^{-kS} , where k is a constant. So now, we will substitute $k \rightarrow -i/\hbar$ in the expression $I = \sqrt{\frac{km}{2\pi(t_b-t_a)}} e^{-\frac{km}{2(t_b-t_a)}(x_b-x_a)^2}$.

Then, the expression for the Kernel or propagator for the free particle between the initial and final points **a** and **b**, denoted by $K_0(b, a)$, is:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i(t_b - t_a)}} e^{\frac{im(x_b-x_a)^2}{2\hbar(t_b-t_a)}}$$

The propagator $K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i(t_b - t_a)}} e^{\frac{im(x_b - x_a)^2}{2\hbar(t_b - t_a)}}$ can be interpreted as the probability amplitude of a free particle going from point **a** to point **b** in spacetime. The square of the modulus of the propagator (or the product of the propagator with its complex conjugate) gives the corresponding probability:

$$|K_0(b, a)|^2 = K_0(b, a)^* K_0(b, a) = \frac{m}{2\pi\hbar(t_b - t_a)}$$

We see that the probability is a real and constant quantity, as expected. The above expression is, more appropriately, the probability density. Let us recall that the probability, by itself, is a conserved quantity. This does not mean that the probability of each path, or the probability of finding the particle at every position in space is the same. To calculate the probability of finding the particle within a particular region in space, we have to integrate the probability density over that region. We also observe that the expression for probability does not depend on the space variable x , even though the probability amplitude (or the propagator) depends on x_a and x_b .

3.3 De Broglie Relation using the Free Particle Propagator

The de Broglie relation, named after Louis de Broglie, is a consequence of wave-particle duality. According to de Broglie's hypothesis, every moving particle has a wave associated with it, and hence a wavelength. The de Broglie equation is the mathematical relation between the wavelength and momentum of a particle, and is given by:

$$p\lambda = h$$

where p is the momentum of the particle, λ is the wavelength of the associated wave and h is Planck's constant. We will now show that one can arrive at the above expression (for a free particle) using the free particle propagator we derived. We have:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i(t_b - t_a)}} e^{\frac{im(x_b - x_a)^2}{2\hbar(t_b - t_a)}}$$

Now, without loss of generality, we set $x_a = 0$, $t_a = 0$, $x_b = x$ and $t_b = t$. Thus, the expression for the free particle propagator becomes:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i t}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

The propagator, expressed in the above form, is the probability amplitude of the free particle moving from $(0,0)$ to (t, x) in the spacetime diagram. The plot of the real part of the propagator multiplied by the square root of the imaginary number, i.e., $Re(\sqrt{i}K_0)$, as a function of the space variable x (for a fixed time t) is shown below.

Figure 12: Plot of $\text{Re}(\sqrt{i}K_0)$ as a function of x . (Source: *Quantum Mechanics and Path Integrals* by Richard Feynman, Albert Hibbs and Daniel Styer.)

In the above plot, we are mainly interested in the behavior of the real part of the propagator as a function of x . We had:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

Multiplying the above equation by \sqrt{i} , we get:

$$\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{i} \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

The real part of the above expression is:

$$\text{Re}[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)] = \text{Re} \left[\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}} \right] = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}} \cos \left(\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t} \right)$$

Let us plot $\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}} \cos \left(\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t} \right)$ as a function of x using Python. The code and output are shown below:

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
m = 1e-31 #arbitrary mass in kg
hbar = 1.05457e-34 #reduced Planck's constant in J-s
t = 1 #arbitrary time in s
x = np.linspace(-0.2,0.2,1000)
K0 = ((m/(2*np.pi*hbar*t))**(0.5))*np.cos(m*x*x/(2*hbar*t))
plt.title("Plot of Re(sqrt(i)K0) as a function of x")
plt.xlabel(r'$x$')
plt.ylabel(r'Re[\sqrt{i} K_0$ (b,a)]')
plt.plot(x,K0, 'g-',lw=2)
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```


From the plot above, we can see that for large values of x on both directions (far from the origin), the distance between the nodes of the periodic function varies very little over a few cycles. This can be translated to the wavelength being small. This intuitively makes sense, because a large value of x indicates the classical particle has moved far away from its initial position (which in this case is $x_a = 0$), which means it has a very high velocity and in turn, a high value of momentum. This means the classical momentum p and the wavelength λ are inversely related; their product must be constant.

Let us now mathematically calculate the wavelength λ , assuming x to be very large. If x is very large as compared to λ , we may replace $x \rightarrow x + \lambda$ in the expression for $K_0(b, a)$ to obtain a new Kernel $K_0'(b, a)$. Since $x \gg \lambda$, we can write:

$$K_0'(b, a) = K_0(b, a)$$

We know that:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

Now, replacing $x \rightarrow x + \lambda$ in the above expression, we get:

$$K_0'(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{im(x+\lambda)^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

Equating $K_0'(b, a)$ and $K_0(b, a)$ and simplifying, we get:

$$e^{\frac{im(x+\lambda)^2}{2\hbar t}} = e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

Multiplying both sides by $e^{-\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$, we get:

$$e^{\frac{im(x+\lambda)^2}{2\hbar t} - \frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}} = 1$$

Using $e^{2\pi i} = 1$, we may write:

$$e^{\frac{im(x+\lambda)^2}{2\hbar t} - \frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}} = e^{2\pi i}$$

This means:

$$\frac{m(x+\lambda)^2}{2\hbar t} - \frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t} = 2\pi$$

$$\frac{m(x^2 + \lambda^2 + 2x\lambda)}{2\hbar t} - \frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t} = \frac{m\lambda^2 + 2mx\lambda}{2\hbar t} = 2\pi$$

Since $\lambda \ll x$, we neglect $m\lambda^2$:

$$\frac{mx\lambda}{\hbar t} = 2\pi$$

Since x is large, we may write $x/t = v$, where v is the classical velocity of the particle. Thus:

$$mv\lambda = 2\pi\hbar$$

Using $\hbar = h/2\pi$, we further simplify the above expression:

$$mv\lambda = h$$

Now, the classical momentum is given by $p = mv$. Hence:

$$p\lambda = h$$

We have arrived at the familiar de Broglie equation. This equation connects the wavelength λ of the quantum wave associated with a particle of mass m and velocity v to its linear momentum $p = mv$.

3.4 Planck-Einstein Relation using the Free Particle Propagator

The Planck-Einstein relation simply states that the energy E carried by a photon is directly proportional to the frequency ν of the associated electromagnetic radiation. Mathematically:

$$E = h\nu$$

This equation reflects the realization that energy is not radiated continuously as predicted by classical physics, but only in discrete packets dubbed “quanta” (the photon is the quantum for light energy). This realization is the starting point of quantum theory.

Let us recall that the free particle moving from $(0,0)$ to (t, x) , is described by the Kernel:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

We will now look at the plot of the real part of the propagator multiplied by the square root of the imaginary number, i.e., $Re(\sqrt{i}K_0)$, as a function of time, for a fixed x .

Figure 13: Plot of $\text{Re}(\sqrt{i}K_0)$ as a function of t . (Source: *Quantum Mechanics and Path Integrals* by Richard Feynman, Albert Hibbs and Daniel Styer.)

Let us generate the above plot: $\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}} \cos\left(\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t}\right)$ as a function of t using Python. The code and output are shown below:

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
m = 1e-31 #arbitrary mass in kg
hbar = 1.05457e-34 #reduced Planck's constant in J-s
x = 1 #arbitrary position in m
t = np.linspace(2.5,30,1000)
K0 = ((m/(2*np.pi*hbar*t))**(0.5))*np.cos(m*x*x/(2*hbar*t))
plt.title("Plot of Re(\sqrt{i}K_0) as a function of t")
plt.xlabel(r'$t$')
plt.ylabel(r'Re[\sqrt{i} K_0$ (b,a)]')
plt.plot(t,K0,'b-',lw=1)
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```


In this case, we notice that the amplitude of the function drops off with time (as t increases). But when t is very large, the amplitudes are relatively constant over a few cycles, and we can approximate the function to be a fixed amplitude periodic function within a certain interval. This means $K_0(b, a)$ approximately repeats itself if t is sufficiently large. Let the time period of the Kernel (the minimum time after which it repeats) be T ($t \gg T$).

Since $t \gg T$, we may put $t \rightarrow t + T$ in the expression for the Kernel $K_0(b, a)$ to get a new Kernel $K_0'(b, a)$. Equating $K_0(b, a)$ and $K_0'(b, a)$, we get:

$$\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i(t+T)}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar(t+T)}}$$

Since $t \gg T$, we may put $t \approx t + T$ and equate:

$$\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i(t+T)}}$$

Using this result in our original expression:

$$e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}} = e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar(t+T)}}$$

Multiplying both sides by $e^{-\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar(t+T)}}$, we get:

$$e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t} - \frac{imx^2}{2\hbar(t+T)}} = 1 = e^{2\pi i}$$

Simplifying, we arrive at:

$$\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t} - \frac{mx^2}{2\hbar(t+T)} = 2\pi$$

Now, consider the expression:

$$\frac{1}{t+T} = \frac{1}{t\left(1+\frac{T}{t}\right)} = \frac{1}{t}\left(1+\frac{T}{t}\right)^{-1} \approx \frac{1}{t}\left(1-\frac{T}{t}\right)$$

To obtain the above expression, we have used $(1+x)^n \approx 1+nx$, if $x \ll 1$. Here, since $t \gg T, \frac{T}{t} \ll$

1. Using this expression for $\frac{1}{t+T}$, we get:

$$\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t} - \frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t}\left(1-\frac{T}{t}\right) = 2\pi$$

Simplifying further:

$$\frac{mx^2T}{2\hbar t^2} = 2\pi$$

Again, using $x/t = v$, we get:

$$\frac{mv^2T}{2\hbar} = 2\pi$$

This means:

$$\frac{mv^2}{2} = \frac{2\pi\hbar}{T} = \frac{h}{T}$$

Now, the left-hand side is the energy for a free particle, which is just $\frac{mv^2}{2}$ or the kinetic energy (the potential energy of a free particle is zero). Also, frequency is defined as $\nu = 1/T$. This finally yields:

$$E = h\nu$$

In this section, we saw how the expression of the free particle propagator is derived. We further derived the de Broglie equation and Planck-Einstein equation for the free particle, using this propagator. In the next section, we will turn our attention to a general particle, for which the potential energy is non-zero. We will see how to deal with the action, and derive the path integral from there, if there is a non-zero potential term in the action.

4. PARTICLES WITH NON-ZERO POTENTIAL ENERGIES

In this section, we will study a particle that has a potential energy varying with position, $V = V(x)$. In this case, the Lagrangian of the particle is given by $L = T - V$, where $V \neq 0$. Obviously, this means the action in the path integral will contain an additional potential energy term.

4.1 Linear and Quadratic Potential Energies

Linear and quadratic potentials are most commonly encountered in the microscopic world. An electron of charge $-q$, under the influence of a constant electric field E , moves in a straight line along the direction of the field. It feels a force qE , and the electron's potential energy is given by $-qEx$, if the electron covers a distance x in the direction of the field. The expression for the electric potential energy, $-qEx$, is a linear function of the distance x . This is an example of a linear potential energy.

We may denote the electron's potential energy in the above scenario as: $V = -kx$, where $k = qE$ is a constant. Thus, the action for an electron moving from spacetime point **a** to spacetime point **b** under the influence of a constant electric field is:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} (T - V) dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 + kx \right] dt$$

Quadratic potential energies are important in the microscopic world because the harmonic potential energy is quadratic in nature, and we often model the structure of crystals as atoms arranged periodically in the form of a lattice, with the atoms connected to one another by springs. This is why we assume the expression for the harmonic potential energy $V = \frac{1}{2}kx^2$ to take into account the vibrations of the atoms. The harmonic potential describes oscillatory or simple harmonic motion, and the expression for the harmonic potential energy is a quadratic function of the position variable x . In this case, the action is given by:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} (T - V) dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2}kx^2 \right] dt$$

There are many other potential energies that become important in certain situations. A common example is the Coulomb potential energy between two charges separated by some distance x (say), which varies inversely with the position variable x . We will not discuss these in detail. Also, we will limit ourselves to time-independent potential energies only (the potential energy would be a function of position only).

4.2 Action with Non-Zero Potential Energy Term

Let us start with a particle of mass m , and an arbitrary, time-independent potential energy $V = V(x)$. The action for this particle is given by:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} (T - V) dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 - V(x) \right] dt$$

The propagator for this particle to move from point \mathbf{a} (t_a, x_a) to point \mathbf{b} (t_b, x_b) in spacetime is given by:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-2} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_1 e^{iS/\hbar}$$

where $S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} (T - V) dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 - V(x) \right] dt$.

As before, we will proceed by dividing the time interval (t_a, t_b) into N equal parts, with the intermediate time points being $t_1, t_2, t_3 \dots t_{N-1}$, and the corresponding x values being $x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_{N-1}$. We will denote the initial and final t and x values as $t_a = t_0, t_b = t_N, x_a = x_0$ and $x_b = x_N$.

Now, we will discretize the action S , which is now not as straightforward as before, because of the presence of the additional potential term. Let us focus on a small segment in the i -th time interval (t_i, t_{i+1}) of a path among all the paths from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} (i is arbitrary). The corresponding position interval is (x_i, x_{i+1}). Thus, essentially we are concentrating on the small portion of this path between the points (t_i, x_i) and (t_{i+1}, x_{i+1}). The slope of this small line segment is $\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_i}{t_{i+1} - t_i} = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_i}{\varepsilon}$ (the separation between any two adjacent time points is ε) and the midpoint is $\left(\frac{t_{i+1} + t_i}{2}, \frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}\right)$.

The particle's kinetic energy for this small portion of the path is:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \frac{1}{2} m \left(\frac{dx}{dt}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} m \left(\frac{x_{i+1} - x_i}{\varepsilon}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} m \frac{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2}{\varepsilon^2}$$

To find the expression for the particle's potential energy, we will focus on the midpoint of this line segment $\left(\frac{t_{i+1} + t_i}{2}, \frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}\right)$. Since we do not know the exact form of this potential energy (whether it is linear, quadratic or something else), we simply assume the potential energy to be a function of the space variable of the midpoint $\frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}$ of this portion of the path between time interval (t_i, t_{i+1}): $V = V\left(\frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}\right)$.

Thus, using $t_{i+1} - t_i = \varepsilon$, the action S_i of the particle for this portion of the path (the i -th line segment) can be written as:

$$S_i = \int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} (T - V) dt = (T - V)\varepsilon = \frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}\right)$$

Adding up the contributions from all such actions S_i 's, $i = 0, 1, 2 \dots N - 1$, we get the expression for the complete discretized action over the entire path ($x_0 = x_a$ and $x_N = x_b$):

$$S = \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_1 - x_a)^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_1 + x_a}{2}\right) \right] + \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_2 - x_1)^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_2 + x_1}{2}\right) \right] + \dots + \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_b - x_{N-1})^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_b + x_{N-1}}{2}\right) \right]$$

Thus, the Kernel is given by:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-2} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_1 e^{iS/\hbar}$$

$$= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \int \dots \iiint dx_{N-1} dx_{N-2} \dots dx_2 dx_1 \left[\frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_1 - x_a)^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_1 + x_a}{2}\right) \right]} \right] \dots \left[\frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_b - x_{N-1})^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_b + x_{N-1}}{2}\right) \right]} \right]$$

Note that there are N terms of the general form $\frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}\right) \right]}$, and thus the normalization factor $\left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N$ is taken care of. The contribution of the i -th line segment (for any i) to the path integral is $\frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}\right) \right]}$, which is the probability amplitude for the particle to move from point (t_i, x_i) to the point (t_{i+1}, x_{i+1}) in the presence of a potential field. In other words, it is the propagator:

$$K(t_{i+1}, x_{i+1}; t_i, x_i) = \frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m}{2} \frac{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2}{\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_{i+1} + x_i}{2}\right) \right]}$$

There are N such infinitesimal-time propagators, because we divided the full interval into N equal parts.

4.3 Path Integral for Linear and Quadratic Potential Energies

Now, we will illustrate a method to evaluate the Kernel (or the path integral) for an action containing linear and quadratic potential energy terms. Evaluating the path integral for a general potential energy is extremely complicated.

First, let us consider a potential energy that is linear in the position variable x : $V = -kx$. The action for a particle of mass m and with a potential energy $V = -kx$, between the points \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , is:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} (T - V) dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 + kx \right] dt$$

The propagator from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} for this particle is given by:

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{A}\right)^N \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-2} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_1 e^{iS/\hbar}$$

Let the path for which the action S is minimum be denoted by \bar{x} . This path is referred to as the least path. Any arbitrary path x between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} can be expressed as:

$$x = \bar{x} + \eta$$

where η is a variation about the least path \bar{x} . Note that the initial and final points \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are fixed. Thus, at $t = t_a$ and $t = t_b$, we must have $x = \bar{x}$. This means $\eta = 0$ for at $t = t_a$ and $t = t_b$.

Expanding the action S about the least path \bar{x} and using $x = \bar{x} + \eta$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 + kx \right] dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d(\bar{x} + \eta)}{dt} \right)^2 + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt \\
&= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} + \frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt
\end{aligned}$$

Simplifying further, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + 2 \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} + \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 \right\} + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt \\
&= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\left\{ \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + k\bar{x} \right\} + m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} + k\eta + \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 \right] dt \\
&= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + k\bar{x} \right] dt + m \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[k\eta + \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 \right] dt
\end{aligned}$$

The first integral in the above expression is essentially the original action S evaluated at the least path $x = \bar{x}$. We will denote it by S_0 .

Let us evaluate the second integral by parts:

$$\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt = \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \eta \Big|_{t_a}^{t_b} - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt$$

Since $\eta = 0$ at $t = t_a$ and $t = t_b$, the first term vanishes. Thus, we finally have $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt = - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt$.

Using this in the original expression for S , we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= S_0 - m \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[k\eta + \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 \right] dt \\
&= S_0 - m \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} k\eta dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 dt \\
&= S_0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} - k \right] dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 dt
\end{aligned}$$

Since S_0 is the action for the least path (the minimum action), $S = S_0$ for up to first order variations η . In other words, the action does not change much around the minima, for up to first order variations η . Let us now also ignore the third term in the above expression, which contains a second order time derivative of η (since we are only talking about first order variations η now). Ignoring the third term and setting $S = S_0$, from the above expression we get:

$$S_0 = S_0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} - k \right] dt$$

This means:

$$\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2 \bar{x}}{dt^2} - k \right] dt = 0$$

Since η is arbitrary, this means:

$$m \frac{d^2 \bar{x}}{dt^2} - k = 0$$

Using this result back in our original expression for the action S , we get:

$$S = S_0 + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 dt$$

Denoting $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 dt$ by S_η , we can now express the action as:

$$S = S_0 + S_\eta$$

Now, using $x = \bar{x} + \eta$, we can write $x_i = \bar{x}_i + \eta_i$, for all the i line segments the path from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} has been divided into. Then, $dx_i = d\bar{x}_i + d\eta_i$. However, $d\bar{x}_i = 0$ for all i , because all \bar{x}_i lie on the least path and are fixed. Thus, we have $dx_i = d\eta_i$ for all i .

Recall the general expression for the propagator from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} :

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{A} \right)^N \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_{N-2} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_1 e^{iS/\hbar}$$

Rewriting this expression after replacing all $dx_i = d\eta_i$ gives us a path integral in terms of η :

$$K(b, a) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{A} \right)^N \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_{N-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_{N-2} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_1 e^{iS/\hbar}$$

Also, using $S = S_0 + S_\eta$, we can write:

$$e^{iS/\hbar} = e^{i(S_0 + S_\eta)/\hbar} = e^{iS_0/\hbar} e^{iS_\eta/\hbar}$$

Note that $e^{iS_0/\hbar}$ is independent of η . Thus, we may express the path integral as:

$$K(b, a) = e^{iS_0/\hbar} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_{N-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_{N-2} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_1 \left(\frac{1}{A} \right)^N e^{iS_\eta/\hbar}$$

We will now treat $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_{N-1} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_{N-2} \dots \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta_1 \left(\frac{1}{A} \right)^N e^{iS_\eta/\hbar}$ as a constant C . It is not possible to exactly evaluate this constant using this method. Thus, we get:

$$K(b, a) = C e^{iS_0/\hbar}$$

Recall that we are currently considering a particle with a linear potential energy $V = -kx$. The action for such a particle, as we have seen, is given by:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 + kx \right] dt$$

We now need to find a \bar{x} that minimizes the action S , where the minimum action is denoted by S_0 :

$$S_0 = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + k\bar{x} \right] dt$$

Let us introduce a small variation η about \bar{x} in x such that: $x = \bar{x} + \eta$. The new action S' will be given by:

$$S' = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d(\bar{x} + \eta)}{dt} \right)^2 + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt$$

Expanding S' about the least path \bar{x} , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S' &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d(\bar{x} + \eta)}{dt} \right)^2 + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} + \frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + 2 \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} + \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 \right\} + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt \end{aligned}$$

Neglecting the higher order term in η , $\left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S' &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + 2 \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} \right\} + k(\bar{x} + \eta) \right] dt \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\left\{ \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + k\bar{x} \right\} + m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} + k\eta \right] dt \end{aligned}$$

Using $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + k\bar{x} \right] dt = S_0$, we get:

$$S' = S_0 + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} + k\eta \right] dt$$

Integrating $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt$ by parts yields:

$$\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt = \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \eta \Big|_{t_a}^{t_b} - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt$$

Again, since $\eta = 0$ at $t = t_a$ and $t = t_b$, the first term vanishes, leaving us with $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt = - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt$. Using this result in our expression for S' , we get:

$$S' = S_0 - m \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} k\eta dt = S_0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} - k \right] dt$$

However, $S' = S_0$ for first order variations about the least path. This means, from the above expression:

$$\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} - k \right] dt = 0$$

Again, since η is arbitrary, this means:

$$m \frac{d^2 \bar{x}}{dt^2} - k = 0 \rightarrow m \frac{d^2 \bar{x}}{dt^2} = k$$

Thus, we finally get a second order differential equation in t :

$$\frac{d^2 \bar{x}}{dt^2} = k'$$

where $k' = k/m$ is a constant.

Integrating the above equation once with respect to t , we get:

$$\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} = k't + c_1$$

where c_1 is the constant of integration. Integrating this equation again with respect to t , we get:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{k't^2}{2} + c_1 t + c_2$$

where c_2 is also an integration constant. The above equation is the equation of a parabola, meaning the least path \bar{x} is a parabola.

Now, let $\bar{x}(t = t_a) = x_a$ and $\bar{x}(t = t_b) = x_b$. Then, putting $t = t_a$ and $\bar{x} = x_a$ in the above equation, we get:

$$x_a = \frac{k't_a^2}{2} + c_1 t_a + c_2$$

Thus, we have:

$$c_2 = x_a - \frac{k't_a^2}{2} - c_1 t_a$$

Now, putting $t = t_b$ and $\bar{x} = x_b$ in the original expression for \bar{x} , we get:

$$x_b = \frac{k't_b^2}{2} + c_1 t_b + c_2$$

Using $c_2 = x_a - \frac{k't_a^2}{2} - c_1 t_a$ in the above expression, we have:

$$x_b = \frac{k't_b^2}{2} + c_1 t_b + x_a - \frac{k't_a^2}{2} - c_1 t_a = \frac{k'}{2} (t_b^2 - t_a^2) + c_1 (t_b - t_a) + x_a$$

From this, we find an expression for c_1 :

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{t_b - t_a} \left[x_b - x_a - \frac{k'}{2} (t_b^2 - t_a^2) \right]$$

Thus, the complete expression for \bar{x} is:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{k't^2}{2} + \frac{t}{t_b - t_a} \left[x_b - x_a - \frac{k'}{2} (t_b^2 - t_a^2) \right] + x_a - \frac{k't_a^2}{2} - \frac{t_a}{t_b - t_a} \left[x_b - x_a - \frac{k'}{2} (t_b^2 - t_a^2) \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{k'}{2} (t^2 - tt_b - tt_a - t_a^2 + t_a t_b + t_a^2) + \frac{x_b - x_a}{t_b - t_a} (t - t_a) + x_a \\
&= \frac{k'}{2} [t^2 - t(t_b + t_a) + t_a t_b] + \frac{x_b - x_a}{t_b - t_a} (t - t_a) + x_a
\end{aligned}$$

Let us now evaluate $\left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt}\right)^2$:

$$\left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt}\right)^2 = \left[\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{k't^2}{2} + c_1 t + c_2 \right) \right]^2 = (k't + c_1)^2 = k'^2 t^2 + 2k'tc_1 + c_1^2$$

We can now express S_0 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_0 &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt}\right)^2 + k\bar{x} \right] dt \\
&= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} (k'^2 t^2 + 2k'tc_1 + c_1^2) + k \left(\frac{k't^2}{2} + c_1 t + c_2 \right) \right] dt \\
&= \frac{m}{2} \left[\frac{k'^2 t^3}{3} + k't^2 c_1 + c_1^2 t \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} + k \left[\frac{k't^3}{6} + \frac{c_1 t^2}{2} + c_2 t \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} \\
&= \frac{m}{2} \left[\frac{k'^2 (t_b^3 - t_a^3)}{3} + k'(t_b^2 - t_a^2) c_1 + c_1^2 (t_b - t_a) \right] + k \left[\frac{k' (t_b^3 - t_a^3)}{6} + \frac{c_1 (t_b^2 - t_a^2)}{2} + c_2 (t_b - t_a) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Now, we assumed $k' = k/m$. Hence, $k = mk'$. Using this and simplifying the above expression, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_0 &= \frac{m}{2} \left[\frac{k'^2 (t_b^3 - t_a^3)}{3} + k'(t_b^2 - t_a^2) c_1 + c_1^2 (t_b - t_a) \right] \\
&\quad + m \left[\frac{k'^2 (t_b^3 - t_a^3)}{6} + \frac{k' (t_b^2 - t_a^2) c_1}{2} + k' c_2 (t_b - t_a) \right] \\
&= \frac{m}{3} k'^2 (t_b^3 - t_a^3) + mk'(t_b^2 - t_a^2) c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} m c_1^2 + m k' c_2 \right) (t_b - t_a)
\end{aligned}$$

where $c_1 = \frac{1}{t_b - t_a} \left[x_b - x_a - \frac{k'}{2} (t_b^2 - t_a^2) \right]$ and $c_2 = x_a - \frac{k' t_a^2}{2} - c_1 t_a$.

Thus, now we can use the above expression for S_0 for a particle with a linear potential energy and write the path integral from **a** to **b** as follows:

$$K(b, a) = C e^{iS_0/\hbar} = C e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m}{3} k'^2 (t_b^3 - t_a^3) + m k' (t_b^2 - t_a^2) c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} m c_1^2 + m k' c_2 \right) (t_b - t_a) \right]}$$

where the expression for the linear potential energy is $-kx$, and $k' = k/m$, m is the mass of the particle.

Note that if we put $k = 0 \rightarrow k' = 0$ in the expression for the least action S_0 , we get:

$$S_0 = \frac{1}{2} m c_1^2 (t_b - t_a)$$

Let us also put $k' = 0$ in the expression for c_1 :

$$c_1 = \frac{x_b - x_a}{t_b - t_a}$$

Thus, the least action becomes:

$$S_0 = \frac{1}{2} m c_1^2 (t_b - t_a) = \frac{1}{2} m \frac{(x_b - x_a)^2}{t_b - t_a}$$

This is precisely the free particle action, which is not surprising because $k = 0$ means $-kx = 0$, meaning that the potential energy is zero, and the particle is a free particle.

Now, let us find the least action for a quadratic potential energy of the form: $V = \frac{1}{2} kx^2$. The expression for the action of a mass m attached to a spring, oscillating back and forth, is:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} (T - V) dt = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} kx^2 \right] dt$$

Again, we will try to find the least path \bar{x} for which the action becomes minimum:

$$S_0 = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\bar{x}^2 \right] dt$$

Let us introduce a small variation η in x about \bar{x} , such that $x = \bar{x} + \eta$, and the new action S' is:

$$S' = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d(\bar{x} + \eta)}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k(\bar{x} + \eta)^2 \right] dt$$

Simplifying the above expression, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S' &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} + \frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k(\bar{x} + \eta)^2 \right] dt \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + 2 \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} + \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 \right\} - \frac{1}{2} k(\bar{x}^2 + 2\bar{x}\eta + \eta^2) \right] dt \end{aligned}$$

Neglecting the higher order term in η , $\left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2$ and η^2 , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S' &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\left(\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} \right) - \frac{1}{2} k(\bar{x}^2 + 2\bar{x}\eta) \right] dt \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\bar{x}^2 \right) dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} - k\bar{x}\eta \right) dt \end{aligned}$$

Using $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\bar{x}^2 \right] dt = S_0$, we get:

$$S' = S_0 + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} - k\bar{x}\eta \right) dt$$

Integrating $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt$ by parts, we get:

$$\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt = \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \eta \Big|_{t_a}^{t_b} - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt$$

Now, since $\eta = 0$ at $t = t_a$ and $t = t_b$, the first term vanishes, leaving us with $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt = - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt$. Using this result in the expression for S' , we get:

$$S' = S_0 - m \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} \eta dt - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} k\bar{x}\eta dt = S_0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} + k\bar{x} \right] dt$$

Since $S' = S_0$ for first order variations about the least path, from the above expression:

$$\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} + k\bar{x} \right] dt = 0$$

And since η is arbitrary, we can conclude:

$$m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} + k\bar{x} = 0 \rightarrow m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} = -k\bar{x}$$

The above equation looks familiar: it's Newton's law of motion for simple harmonic oscillations! If we assume the least path \bar{x} to be the displacement of the mass m with spring constant k undergoing simple harmonic oscillation, then $m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2}$ is the force (mass times acceleration), which, for simple harmonic oscillations is $-k\bar{x}$, as we know. The solution of the above equation is given by:

$$\bar{x} = A\cos(\omega t) + B\sin(\omega t)$$

where $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$, and the constants A and B can be determined by using the conditions $\bar{x}(t = t_a) = x_a$ and $\bar{x}(t = t_b) = x_b$. Let us assume $(t_a, x_a) = (0, 0)$. This means $\bar{x}(t = 0) = 0$ and $\bar{x}(t = t_b) = x_b$.

Putting $\bar{x} = 0$ and $t = 0$ in the expression $\bar{x} = A\cos(\omega t) + B\sin(\omega t)$, we get:

$$0 = A\cos(0) + B\sin(0) = A$$

Thus, $A = 0$. Now, let us put $A = 0$, $\bar{x} = x_b$ and $t = t_b$ in the expression for \bar{x} :

$$x_b = B\sin(\omega t_b)$$

This means $B = \frac{x_b}{\sin(\omega t_b)}$, and our final solution is:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{x_b}{\sin(\omega t_b)} \sin(\omega t)$$

Let us now evaluate $\left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt}\right)^2$:

$$\left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt}\right)^2 = \left[\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{x_b}{\sin(\omega t_b)} \sin(\omega t) \right) \right]^2 = \left[\frac{\omega x_b}{\sin(\omega t_b)} \cos(\omega t) \right]^2$$

Now, we had:

$$S_0 = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k \bar{x}^2 \right] dt$$

Using the above results, we may express S_0 as:

$$\begin{aligned} S_0 &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{\omega x_b}{\sin(\omega t_b)} \cos(\omega t) \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k \left(\frac{x_b}{\sin(\omega t_b)} \sin(\omega t) \right)^2 \right] dt \\ &= \frac{m}{2} \frac{\omega^2 x_b^2}{\sin^2(\omega t_b)} \left[\frac{t}{2} + \frac{\sin(2\omega t)}{4\omega} \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} - \frac{1}{2} k \frac{x_b^2}{\sin^2(\omega t_b)} \left[\frac{t}{2} - \frac{\sin(2\omega t)}{4\omega} \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} \end{aligned}$$

Using $\omega^2 = k/m$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S_0 &= \frac{kx_b^2}{2 \sin^2(\omega t_b)} \left[\frac{t}{2} + \frac{\sin(2\omega t)}{4\omega} \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} - \frac{kx_b^2}{2 \sin^2(\omega t_b)} \left[\frac{t}{2} - \frac{\sin(2\omega t)}{4\omega} \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} \\ &= \frac{kx_b^2}{2 \sin^2(\omega t_b)} \left[\frac{t}{2} + \frac{\sin(2\omega t)}{4\omega} - \left(\frac{t}{2} - \frac{\sin(2\omega t)}{4\omega} \right) \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} \\ &= \frac{kx_b^2}{2 \sin^2(\omega t_b)} \left[\frac{\sin(2\omega t)}{2\omega} \right]_{t_a}^{t_b} = \frac{kx_b^2}{2 \sin^2(\omega t_b)} \left[\frac{\sin(2\omega t_b)}{2\omega} - \frac{\sin(2\omega t_a)}{2\omega} \right] \\ &= \frac{kx_b^2}{4\omega \sin^2(\omega t_b)} [\sin(2\omega t_b) - \sin(2\omega t_a)] \end{aligned}$$

Now, recall that we assumed $t_a = 0$. Using $t_a = 0$ and $k = \omega^2 m$, we get:

$$S_0 = \frac{m\omega x_b^2}{4 \sin^2(\omega t_b)} \sin(2\omega t_b)$$

Using $\sin(2x) = 2\sin(x) \cos(x)$, we get:

$$S_0 = \frac{m\omega x_b^2}{4 \sin^2(\omega t_b)} 2\sin(\omega t_b) \cos(\omega t_b) = \frac{m\omega x_b^2 \cos(\omega t_b)}{2\sin(\omega t_b)}$$

The assumption $(t_a, x_a) = (0, 0)$ reflects that the body starts to oscillate from the mean position (origin).

Note that in the limit $\omega \rightarrow 0$, $\cos(\omega t_b) \rightarrow 1$ and $\sin(\omega t_b) \rightarrow \omega t_b$, and the above expression reduces to:

$$S_0 = \frac{m\omega x_b^2}{2\omega t_b} = \frac{m x_b^2}{2 t_b} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{m x_b^2}{t_b}$$

This is the action for a free particle (keep in mind that here we have assumed $t_a = 0, x_a = 0$), which makes sense, because $\omega \rightarrow 0$ implies $k \rightarrow 0$, meaning $\frac{1}{2} k x^2 \rightarrow 0$, meaning there is no potential energy, and the particle is effectively a free particle.

Now, we calculate the propagator for a particle with a quadratic potential energy in the same method that we employed for linear potential energy. We start with $S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} kx^2 \right] dt$ and replace $x = \bar{x} + \eta$, where \bar{x} is the least path and η is an arbitrary variation about the least path, with the endpoints remaining fixed. The action corresponding to the least path \bar{x} is the minimum action, denoted by S_0 . If we can express the total action as $S = S_0 + S_\eta$, where S_η depends entirely on η , then the propagator $K(b, a)$ can be expressed as $C e^{iS_0/\hbar}$, where we treat C to be constant, as we saw in the case of linear potential energy.

We proceed as follows:

$$S = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d(\bar{x} + \eta)}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k(\bar{x} + \eta)^2 \right] dt$$

Simplifying the above expression, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} + \frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k(\bar{x} + \eta)^2 \right] dt \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left[\frac{m}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 + 2 \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} + \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 \right\} - \frac{1}{2} k(\bar{x}^2 + 2\bar{x}\eta + \eta^2) \right] dt \end{aligned}$$

Regrouping the terms, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\bar{x}^2 \right) dt + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} - k\bar{x}\eta \right) dt + \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \left(\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\eta^2 \right) dt \\ &= S_0 + \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(m \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} - k\bar{x}\eta \right) dt + \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \left(\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\eta^2 \right) dt \end{aligned}$$

As we have seen previously, $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\bar{x}}{dt} \frac{d\eta}{dt} dt = - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} dt$, which means:

$$S = S_0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} + k\bar{x} \right] dt + \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \left(\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\eta^2 \right) dt$$

Now, ignoring the last integral which contains second order terms in η , and considering that $S = S_0$ for up to first order variations η , we get:

$$S_0 = S_0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \eta \left[m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} + k\bar{x} \right] dt$$

Since η is arbitrary, this means:

$$m \frac{d^2\bar{x}}{dt^2} + k\bar{x} = 0$$

Using this result in our original expression for S , we get:

$$S = S_0 + \int_{x_a}^{x_b} \left(\frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{d\eta}{dt} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} k\eta^2 \right) dt = S_0 + S_\eta$$

Thus, we can express the Kernel for a particle of mass m , spring constant k and with a potential energy $\frac{1}{2}kx^2$ to move from point \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{b} as:

$$K(b, a) = C e^{iS_0/\hbar}$$

Using the previously obtained expression for S_0 for quadratic potential energy, we can finally write:

$$K(b, a) = C e^{iS_0/\hbar} = C e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m\omega x_b^2 \cos(\omega t_b)}{2 \sin(\omega t_b)} \right]}$$

In this section, we studied path integrals for particles with a non-zero potential energy, in particular linear and quadratic potential energies. In the next section, we will first look at how the propagator in path integrals is different from the familiar wave function that is used in canonical quantum mechanics. Then, we will derive the Schrödinger equation – both for a free particle and a particle with a non-zero potential energy – using path integrals.

5. THE SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

In this section, we will try to understand the fundamental difference between the propagator in path integrals and the wave function in canonical quantum mechanics, even though both of them are probability amplitudes. Using Python, we will plot the expressions for both the propagator as well as the wave function for a free particle as functions of position and time, and compare them visually. Next, we will arrive at the Schrödinger equation – first with no potential energy term (for a free particle) and then the general expression – using the respective propagators.

5.1 The Wave Function and the Propagator

In the canonical formulation of quantum mechanics, the wave function of a system, denoted by ψ , essentially contains all the information that can be known about that system. However, by itself ψ has no physical significance. The square of the modulus of ψ can be interpreted as some probability (or probability density, more appropriately). ψ roughly translates to the amplitude of the quantum mechanical wave describing the system, and is allowed to take on both positive and negative values, and ψ can also be a complex quantity in general. However, probability is always a real and positive quantity. Notice that $|\psi|^2 = \psi^* \psi$ is always positive and real, where ψ^* is the complex conjugate of ψ .

The wave function ψ is a function of position and time, and is expressed as $\psi = \psi(x, t)$. $\psi(x, t)$ is the wave function of the system at the spacetime point (t, x) , and $|\psi(x, t)|^2$ gives the probability of finding the system at (t, x) . Usually in quantum mechanics, we do not speak about finding a particle at a specific point in spacetime, owing to the uncertainty principle. A more meaningful question to ask is: What is the probability of finding this particle within the region in space between x to $x + dx$? If $\psi(x, t)$ is the wave function that describes this particle, then the answer to this question would be $|\psi(x, t)|^2 dx$. This is why $|\psi(x, t)|^2$ can be thought of as some probability density.

A basic constraint on any physical system is that it must exist somewhere in space. In other words, if we consider all the space in the universe, then the probability of finding the system within the entire universe must be 1. Mathematically:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\psi(x, t)|^2 dx = 1$$

This is the normalization condition. A wave function describing a physical system must satisfy the above condition, and we say that the wave function is normalized. This ensures that if we calculate the probability of finding the system in some finite region of space, we always get a value between 0 and 1. If we consider all of space, then of course we get a probability of exactly 1.

Since the wave function is theorized to be essentially a wave, we start by assuming that ψ is described by the classical expression of a wave:

$$\psi = A e^{i(kx - \omega t)}$$

Here, A is a constant, which is chosen such that ψ is normalized. Here, for simplicity, we have assumed that the wave is propagating only in one dimension (along the x direction), and the phase of the wave is $(kx - \omega t)$, where k is the wave propagation constant, and ω is the angular frequency. The exact form of the wave function for a particular system can be obtained by solving the Schrödinger equation with appropriate boundary conditions.

It is interesting and important to note that Schrödinger did not derive his equation. In fact, the Schrödinger equation is a fundamental postulate of quantum mechanics; even though we can arrive at the equation for some specific cases, the equation cannot be rigorously derived from some more fundamental principle. The role played by Schrödinger equation in canonical quantum mechanics is similar to the role played by the equation $F = ma = m \frac{dx^2}{dt^2}$ in classical mechanics: it dictates how the system evolves over time. Whereas $F = ma$ tells how the position x of a classical system of mass m changes with time, if the system is under the influence of a force F , Schrödinger equation tells how the wave function ψ of a quantum mechanical system evolves with time.

Note that the equation $F = m \frac{dx^2}{dt^2}$ is a second order differential equation in time. Schrödinger equation, however, is a second-order differential equation in the space variable x . Schrödinger equation in one dimension (x) for a system of mass m , potential energy V and described by the wave function ψ is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + V\psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

Note that the equation contains a second order derivative in the space variable x , but a first order derivative in time t . Roughly speaking, this means Schrödinger equation does not keep space and time on equal footing, unlike Albert Einstein's special theory of relativity, where time is treated as the fourth dimension, on the same footing as the three space dimensions. This is why Schrödinger equation is non-relativistic, meaning it cannot be applied to situations where the modifications on spacetime demanded by relativity become significant, like at near-light velocities.

The form of the kinetic energy operator that is used in Schrödinger equation is based on the classical expression for kinetic energy:

$$T = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

where $p = mv$ is the linear momentum of the system of mass m and velocity v . Notice that the kinetic energy is a quadratic function of the momentum p . In special relativity, however, the total energy of a system (ignoring the potential energy) is given by:

$$E = \sqrt{m^2c^4 + p^2c^2}$$

where m is the intrinsic mass of the system when it is at rest, $p = \gamma mv$ is the relativistic momentum of the system, where the factor $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, and c is the speed of light in vacuum, which is constant. Notice that due to the square root, here the energy E is no longer a quadratic function of p .

Schrödinger equation is still an adequate framework for dealing with most quantum mechanical problems, and remains as relevant today as it was when Schrödinger introduced it almost a century ago. However, Schrödinger equation must be modified if special relativity and quantum mechanics are to be reconciled. This was achieved by the Dirac equation, which was the first, albeit primitive, version of a quantum field theory.

Now, we will look at the basic difference between the wave function, which is of central importance in canonical quantum mechanics, and the propagator in the path integral formulation. We will confine our discussion to the free particle. Recall that the expression for the free particle propagator in the path integral formulation is:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i(t_b - t_a)}} e^{\frac{im(x_b - x_a)^2}{2\hbar(t_b - t_a)}}$$

This is essentially the probability amplitude for a free particle of mass m to move from point $\mathbf{a}(t_a, x_a)$ to point $\mathbf{b}(t_b, x_b)$ in spacetime. When discussing the free particle propagator previously, we had assumed, without loss of generality, that $x_a = 0$, $t_a = 0$, $x_b = x$ and $t_b = t$. This simplifies the expression of the propagator:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

However, keep in mind that in the above expression, x and t are actually space and time intervals, not fixed points. To study the physical behavior of the free particle, we may plot the real part of its propagator as functions of position and time, as we have already done previously. We essentially consider $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$, which is:

$$Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)] = Re\left[\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}\right] = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}} \cos\left(\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t}\right)$$

Now, let us look at the general expression of the free particle wave function:

$$\psi = Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)}$$

From de Broglie's equation, we know that for a particle with linear momentum p and wavelength λ (h is Planck's constant):

$$\frac{h}{p} = \lambda$$

Also, for a wave with wavelength λ and propagation constant k :

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{k}$$

Thus, we may write:

$$\frac{h}{p} = \frac{2\pi}{k} \rightarrow \frac{h}{2\pi} = \frac{p}{k} \rightarrow \hbar = \frac{p}{k}$$

where $\hbar = h/2\pi$ is the reduced Planck constant. Thus, we get: $p = \hbar k$.

Now, from Planck-Einstein equation, we know that for a system with energy E and frequency ν :

$$E = h\nu$$

The angular frequency of a wave $\omega = 2\pi\nu$. Using this result in the above equation, we get:

$$E = \frac{h}{2\pi} 2\pi\nu = \hbar\omega$$

Now, using $p = \hbar k$ and $E = \hbar\omega$ in the expression for ψ , we get:

$$\psi = Ae^{i(kx - \omega t)} = Ae^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(px - Et)}$$

Now, for a free particle, $p = mv = m\frac{x}{t}$ and $E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \frac{1}{2}m\left(\frac{x}{t}\right)^2 = \frac{mx^2}{2t^2}$. Using these results and considering only the real part of the wave function, we get:

$$Re[\psi] = Re\left[Ae^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(px-Et)}\right] = A\cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}(px-Et)\right] = A'\cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\left(\frac{mx^2}{t} - \frac{mx^2}{2t}\right)\right]$$

Since the normalization constant A is complex in general, A' in the expression above is the real part of A . Simplifying the above expression further, we get:

$$Re[\psi] = A\cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\left(\frac{mx^2}{t} - \frac{mx^2}{2t}\right)\right] = A\cos\left(\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t}\right)$$

Notice that the phase $\frac{mx^2}{2\hbar t}$ in the above expression is the same as the phase in the expression for $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$. Now, to visually compare the free particle propagator and the free particle wave function, we need to plot both $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$ and $Re[\psi]$ as functions of both x and t . However, we must keep in mind that we are only interested in studying the behavior of the real parts of the propagator and wave functions and make some general comments about the same. A physical interpretation may not be possible, because a free particle wave function cannot be normalized; hence a finite value of the normalization constant A does not exist (for the case of the free particle). A free particle is not under the influence of any potential, and is free to be at any point in space. Let us try to normalize the wave function $\psi = Ae^{i(kx-\omega t)}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\psi|^2 dx &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \psi^* \psi dx = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (Ae^{i(kx-\omega t)})^* Ae^{i(kx-\omega t)} dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} Ae^{-i(kx-\omega t)} Ae^{i(kx-\omega t)} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |A|^2 dx = |A|^2 [x]_{-\infty}^{+\infty} = \infty\end{aligned}$$

The above integral diverges, meaning it is not possible to normalize the free particle wave function. However, for our purposes here, it is sufficient to note that the normalization constant A that appears in the wave function is always independent of time, and for generating the plots, we will arbitrarily choose a finite value of A , ignoring the fact that the free particle wave function cannot be normalized. We have already generated a plot of $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$ as a function of x . It is shown below once more:

Now, let us generate a plot of $Re[\psi]$ as a function of x using Python. The code and output are shown below:

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
m = 1e-31 #arbitrary mass in kg
hbar = 1.05457e-34 #reduced Planck's constant in J-s
t = 1 #arbitrary time in s
x = np.linspace(-0.2,0.2,1000)
A = 0.5 #arbitrary value of normalization constant
Psi = A*np.cos((m*x*x/(hbar*t))-(m*x*x/(2*hbar*t)))
plt.title("Plot of Re(Ψ) as a function of x")
plt.xlabel(r'$x$')
plt.ylabel(r'$Re[\Psi(x,t)]$')
plt.plot(x,Psi, 'g-',lw=2)
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```


The nature of both the plots are the same. The amplitudes of the plots are different, as expected, because we arbitrarily chose $A = 0.5$ in our code. The numerical value of the amplitude in the free particle propagator, $\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}}$, is not the same as 0.5. Varying the value of A will result in different amplitudes, but the nature of the plot would remain the same.

The important point is that the amplitude A is not a function of time, whereas the amplitude for the free particle propagator, $\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar t}}$, is clearly a function of time. This difference between the propagator and the wave function can be visualized if we look at their plots as a function of time.

We have previously generated a plot of $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$ as a function of t . The output is shown below:

Now, let us generate a plot of $Re[\psi]$ as a function of t using Python. The code and output are shown below:

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
m = 1e-31 #arbitrary mass in kg
hbar = 1.05457e-34 #reduced Planck's constant in J-s
x = 1 #arbitrary position in m
t = np.linspace(0.01,30,10000)
A = 0.5 #arbitrary value of normalization constant
Psi = A*np.cos((m*x*x/(hbar*t))-(m*x*x/(2*hbar*t)))
plt.title("Plot of Re( $\Psi$ ) as a function of t")
plt.xlabel(r'$t$')
plt.ylabel(r'$Re[\Psi(x,t)]$')
plt.plot(t,Psi, 'b-', lw=1)
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```


Here, we clearly see a difference between the two plots. In both cases, we see that the wavelength increases with increasing time (along the positive direction of the horizontal axis). This is because as t increases, the frequency ν decreases, implying a decrease in energy ($E = h\nu$), and an increase in the wavelength λ (frequency and wavelength are inversely related). However, in the plot of the propagator, we see that the amplitude decays over time, whereas for the wave function, the amplitude remains constant throughout. Mathematically, this is obviously because the amplitude of the real part of the free particle propagator, unlike the normalization factor A in the real part of the wave function, is a function of time:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}} e^{\frac{imx^2}{2\hbar t}}$$

Physically also, this makes sense. Recall that in the expression of the free particle propagator, the x and t were space and time intervals, respectively, and not just points. Thus, in the $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$ versus t plot, an increase in t means a longer time interval. The quantity plotted along the vertical axis, $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$, relates to the probability amplitude for the particle moving from point \mathbf{a} to point \mathbf{b} . The longer the time interval between the initial and final points, the less the probability that particle will end up at the same final point from the initial point. Hence, the amplitude of the $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$ versus t plot decays with increasing t . The wave function, on the other hand, by itself contains no information about the time evolution of the particle. To find out how the particle would evolve with time, we need to solve Schrödinger equation for the particle, using the appropriate conditions. Thus, the $Re[\psi]$ versus t plot, by itself, does not contain any information about the time evolution of the particle.

In case of the plots as functions of x , the nature of the plots was the same in both cases, because we have plotted $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$ for a fixed time (a fixed time interval, more precisely). Notice that in both the $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$ versus x and the $Re[\psi]$ versus x plots, the wavelength decreases as x increases, in both directions. From de Broglie's equation $\lambda = h/p$, we see that a decrease in the wavelength λ implies an increase in the momentum of the particle p . This makes sense, because we are looking at the entire region of space (all values of x) for a fixed time. A high value of x indicates the particle travels a longer distance, for which it must have high momentum.

Thus, one of the fundamental differences between the propagator and the wave function is that in the propagator, time evolution is imbibed; the amplitude of $Re[\sqrt{i}K_0(b, a)]$, $\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar it}}$, is a function of time.

In case of the wave function, the normalization constant A is not a function of time, even for time-dependent Hamiltonians. For a given wave function, only after solving the Schrödinger equation can we get the time-evolved wave function. The wave function is a local description of a quantum state, and it gives the probability amplitude for a particle's position (or any other observable) at a specific point in space and time. The propagator, on the other hand, is a global entity that describes the evolution of a quantum system from one point in spacetime to another. It represents the probability amplitude for a particle to evolve from one state (position and time) to another.

5.2 Schrödinger Equation for a Free Particle

We have seen that Schrödinger equation in one dimension (x) for a system of mass m , potential energy V and described by the wave function ψ is given by:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + V\psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

For a free particle, the potential energy $V = 0$. Hence, Schrödinger equation for a free particle, in one dimension, is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

We will not show that one can arrive at the above equation using the free particle propagator. The propagator, as we discussed, gives us the probability amplitude for a particle to move from one spacetime point to another. The wave function gives the probability amplitude for a particle to be at a specific point in spacetime. Unlike a propagator, a wave function does not contain any information about the initial state of the system; in other words, where the system came from. The wave function $\psi(x, t)$ is only concerned about the probability amplitude for finding the system at the spacetime point (t, x) . The probability for the same is given by $|\psi(x, t)|^2$. We will try to derive a differential equation for $\psi(x, t)$, and see if it is the expected Schrödinger equation.

Let us recall the multiplicative law of propagators:

$$K(b, a) = \int dx_c K(b, c)K(c, a)$$

Here, **a** and **b** are the initial and final points, respectively, and **c** is an intermediate point. Let us replace the propagators $K(c, a)$ and $K(b, a)$ by the wave functions $\psi(c)$ and $\psi(b)$, respectively. When we are talking in terms of wave functions, we no longer worry about the initial point **a**. Thus, we can rewrite the multiplicative law in terms of wave functions as:

$$\psi(b) = \int dx_c K(b, c)\psi(c)$$

Let **c** be the spacetime point (t, x_c) . The wave function at (t, x_c) is $\psi(t, x_c)$. Now, since **b** is ahead of **c** in space and time, let **b** be the spacetime point $(t + \varepsilon, x)$, $x > x_c$. Thus, $\psi(b) = \psi(t + \varepsilon, x)$. So, $K(b, c)$ essentially takes the wavefunction from $c(t, x_c)$ to $b(t + \varepsilon, x)$.

We can rewrite $\psi(b) = \int dx_c K(b, c)\psi(c)$ as:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \int dx_c K(t + \varepsilon, x; t, x_c)\psi(t, x_c)$$

From now on, let us denote x_c by the variable y . Recall that we need to take into account all possible x_c , hence it is a variable. Thus, now we may write:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \int dy K(t + \varepsilon, x; t, y)\psi(t, y)$$

The expression for the free particle propagator is:

$$K_0(b, a) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i(t_b - t_a)}} e^{\frac{im(x_b - x_a)^2}{2\hbar(t_b - t_a)}}$$

Setting $t_b = t + \varepsilon$, $t_a = t$, $x_b = x$ and $x_a = y$ in the above expression, we get:

$$K_0(t + \varepsilon, x; t, y) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} e^{\frac{im(x-y)^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}}$$

Note that since $t_b = t + \varepsilon$ and $t = t_a$, we have $t_b = t_a + \varepsilon$, or $t_b - t_a = \varepsilon$.

Using the above expression for $K_0(t + \varepsilon, x; t, y)$ in the equation for $\psi(t + \varepsilon, x)$, we get:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int dy e^{\frac{im(x-y)^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \psi(t, y)$$

Here, y is the integration variable, and x is the fixed endpoint; we want to calculate $\psi(t + \varepsilon, x)$, the probability amplitude at x .

Let us define a new variable $\eta = y - x$. This means $y = x + \eta$ and $d\eta = dy$ (x is constant). In terms of η , we can rewrite the above integral as:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x + \eta)$$

The limits of the integration are not affected by the above change in variable, and are from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$.

Now, the Taylor expansion of $\psi(t + \varepsilon, x)$, up to the first order term, is:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

And the Taylor expansion of $\psi(t, x + \eta)$ up to the second order term is:

$$\psi(t, x + \eta) = \psi(t, x) + \eta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{\eta^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2}$$

Using these two results, we can rewrite $\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x + \eta)$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} &= \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \left[\psi(t, x) + \eta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{\eta^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \right] \\ \psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} &= \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x) \\ &+ \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int \eta d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int \eta^2 d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \end{aligned}$$

In the above equation, $\psi(x, t)$ and its derivatives are treated as constants, because the integration is over η . Recall that x is the fixed endpoint; hence it is a constant.

Let us now focus on the first term on the right-hand side:

$$\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x) \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}}$$

From Gaussian integrals (see Appendix 1), we know that:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx = \sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$$

Let $-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} = \frac{im}{2\hbar\varepsilon}$, meaning $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}}$ (we have used $i^2 = -1$).

Let us start with the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{\eta^2}{2\sigma^2}} d\eta$, and put $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}}$:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{m\eta^2}{2i\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta$$

We know that this equals $\sigma\sqrt{2\pi} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}}$; thus the first term in our expression becomes:

$$\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x) \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x) \sqrt{\frac{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}} = \psi(t, x)$$

The second term in our expression is:

$$\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int \eta d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} \int \eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta$$

This term is zero, because the integrand $\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}}$ is an odd function in η , and the integration limits are from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$.

The third term in our expression is:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \int \eta^2 d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar i\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} \int \eta^2 e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta$$

Using Gaussian integrals, we derived the following result in Appendix 1:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx = \sigma^2$$

Replacing $x \rightarrow \eta$ in the above result, we get:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \eta^2 e^{-\eta^2/2\sigma^2} d\eta = \sigma^2$$

Now, we will put $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}}$ in the above expression:

$$\sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \eta^2 e^{-m\eta^2/2i\hbar\varepsilon} d\eta = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \eta^2 e^{im\eta^2/2\hbar\varepsilon} d\eta = \frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}$$

Rearranging the above expression:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \eta^2 e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta = \sqrt{2\pi} \left(\frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}$$

The third term in our expression was:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \int \eta^2 e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta$$

Using the above result, we may write the third term as:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \sqrt{2\pi} \left(\frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} = \frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2}$$

Note that although we started with a second order derivative in the space variable x , the final expression is first order in time ε .

Now that we have separately evaluated all three terms in the right-hand side of our original expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} &= \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x) \\ &+ \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}} \int \eta d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}} \int \eta^2 d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} \end{aligned}$$

let us put everything together:

$$\psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \psi(t, x) + \frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2}$$

Cancelling the common term $\psi(t, x)$ from both sides:

$$\varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2}$$

Simplifying the above expression, we get:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2}$$

Multiplying both sides of the above equation by $i\hbar$, we get:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2}$$

This is precisely the Schrödinger equation for a free particle (in one dimension) that we have seen before.

5.3 Schrödinger Equation for a Particle in a Potential Field

We have already studied path integrals for particles with potential energy, in particular linear and quadratic potential energies. Now, finally, we will derive Schrödinger equation for a particle with a non-zero potential energy. We will focus on the i -th line segment of a path between the initial and final points, corresponding to the time interval (t_i, t_{i+1}) , and consider the infinitesimal-time propagator for a particle with potential energy $V = V\left(\frac{x_{i+1}+x_i}{2}\right)$:

$$K(t_{i+1}, x_{i+1}; t_i, x_i) = \frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m(x_{i+1}-x_i)^2}{2\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x_{i+1}+x_i}{2}\right) \right]}$$

where $t_{i+1} - t_i = \varepsilon$, or $t_{i+1} = t_i + \varepsilon$.

Rewriting the propagator using $t_i = t$, $x_i = y$, $t_{i+1} = t + \varepsilon$ and $x_{i+1} = x$, we get:

$$K(t + \varepsilon, x; t, y) = \frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m(x-y)^2}{2\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x+y}{2}\right) \right]}$$

Let us recall that:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \int dy K(t + \varepsilon, x; t, y) \psi(t, y)$$

Using $K(t + \varepsilon, x; t, y) = \frac{1}{A} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m(x-y)^2}{2\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x+y}{2}\right) \right]}$ in the above expression, we get:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \frac{1}{A} \int dy e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\frac{m(x-y)^2}{2\varepsilon} - \varepsilon V\left(\frac{x+y}{2}\right) \right]} \psi(t, y)$$

As before, let us introduce a new variable $\eta = y - x$, and using $d\eta = dy$ (x is the fixed final endpoint; hence constant). In terms of η , we can rewrite the above integral as (the limits are from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$):

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \frac{1}{A} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} e^{-\frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar} V\left(x+\frac{\eta}{2}\right)} \psi(t, \eta + x)$$

Taylor expanding $\psi(t + \varepsilon, x)$ up to the first order term, we get:

$$\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

Now, Taylor expanding $\psi(t, x + \eta)$ up to the second order term gives us:

$$\psi(t, x + \eta) = \psi(t, x) + \eta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{\eta^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2}$$

We also Taylor expand $e^{-\frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar} V\left(x+\frac{\eta}{2}\right)}$ up to the first order term, using $e^x = 1 + x$:

$$e^{-\frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar} V\left(x+\frac{\eta}{2}\right)} = 1 - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar} V\left(x + \frac{\eta}{2}\right)$$

Now, further Taylor expanding $V\left(x + \frac{\eta}{2}\right)$ in the above expression, up to the second order term:

$$e^{-\frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}V\left(x+\frac{\eta}{2}\right)} = 1 - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}V\left(x + \frac{\eta}{2}\right) = 1 - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}\left[V(x) + \frac{\eta}{2}\frac{dV}{dx} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\eta}{2}\right)^2\frac{d^2V}{dx^2}\right]$$

Using all these results in $\psi(t + \varepsilon, x) = \frac{1}{A} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} e^{-\frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}V\left(x+\frac{\eta}{2}\right)}\psi(t, \eta + x)$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} &= \frac{1}{A} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \left\{ 1 - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}\left[V(x) + \frac{\eta}{2}\frac{dV}{dx} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\eta}{2}\right)^2\frac{d^2V}{dx^2}\right] \right\} \left(\psi(t, x) + \eta \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} + \frac{\eta^2}{2}\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{A} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \left[\psi(x, t) + \eta \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} + \frac{\eta^2}{2}\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}V(x)\psi(t, x) - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}V(x)\eta \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}V(x)\frac{\eta^2}{2}\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} \right. \\ &\quad - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}\frac{\eta}{2}\frac{dV}{dx}\psi(t, x) - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}\frac{\eta^2}{2}\frac{dV}{dx}\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} - \frac{i\varepsilon}{\hbar}\frac{\eta^3}{4}\frac{dV}{dx}\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{i\varepsilon}{2\hbar}\left(\frac{\eta}{2}\right)^2\frac{d^2V}{dx^2}\psi(t, x) \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{i\varepsilon}{2\hbar}\left(\frac{\eta}{2}\right)^2\eta\frac{d^2V}{dx^2}\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} - \frac{i\varepsilon}{4\hbar}\left(\frac{\eta}{2}\right)^2\eta^2\frac{d^2V}{dx^2}\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

All the terms that do not depend on η , like $V(x)$, $\frac{dV}{dx}$, $\frac{d^2V}{dx^2}$, $\psi(t, x)$, $\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x}$, $\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial x^2}$, are treated as constants. Also notice that no term in the right-hand side of the above expression, other than $\frac{1}{A} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} \psi(t, x)$ has the form $C\psi(t, x)$, where C is an arbitrary constant. No other term on the right-hand side is solely a function of $\psi(t, x)$, without involving its derivatives or $V(x)$ and its derivatives. Comparing with the left-hand side, we see that:

$$\frac{1}{A} \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} = 1$$

Thus, using the previously-obtained result $\int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}}$, we get:

$$A = \int d\eta e^{\frac{im\eta^2}{2\hbar\varepsilon}} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}}$$

We can also write:

$$\frac{1}{A} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}}$$

This is the same expression that we have used in case of the free particle. The above expression for the normalization constant holds true for path integrals in general, regardless of whether we are dealing with a free particle or a particle with a non-zero potential energy.

Now, we will individually look at the terms of the expression that we have obtained. The integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\eta e^{im\eta^2/2\hbar\varepsilon} \eta$ equals zero, and so does all the terms containing this integral, since the integrand is an odd function in η .

In the derivation of the free particle Schrödinger equation, we have already seen that:

$$\frac{1}{A} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \eta^2 e^{-m\eta^2/2i\hbar\varepsilon} d\eta = \frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}$$

Now, let us focus on the integral:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{\frac{-m\eta^2}{2i\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta$$

We have previously evaluated this integral:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{\frac{-m\eta^2}{2i\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}}$$

Using $\frac{1}{A} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar\varepsilon}}$, we may write:

$$\frac{1}{A} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{\frac{-m\eta^2}{2i\hbar\varepsilon}} d\eta = 1$$

Using the above results, and keeping only terms that are linear in ε , we get:

$$\psi(t, x) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \psi(t, x) + \frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{i}{\hbar} \varepsilon V(x) \psi$$

Simplifying the above expression, we get:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \frac{i\hbar}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - \frac{i}{\hbar} V(x) \psi$$

Multiplying both sides of the above expression by $i\hbar$, we get:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + V(x) \psi$$

This is precisely the general form of Schrödinger equation in one dimension, for a particle of mass m , potential energy V and described by the wave function ψ .

In this section, we first studied the difference between the wave function that appears in Schrödinger equation, and the propagator in path integrals. Then we derived Schrödinger equation, both for a free particle and a particle with a non-zero potential energy, using the propagator. This helps us appreciate the beautiful equivalence, yet contrast between the canonical formulation of quantum mechanics and Feynman's path integral formulation.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Quantum mechanics is one of the most revolutionary theories in the history of physics, and arguably all of science. On one hand, it has not only passed many stringent experimental tests, it has also birthed so many advanced technologies. On the other hand, however, many predictions of quantum mechanics are counterintuitive. Feynman himself remarked that anyone who claims to understand quantum mechanics actually understands nothing of it! Just like we can use a computer without a thorough knowledge of its inner workings, physicists have successfully used quantum mechanics in many areas of science and technology without understanding all aspects of the theory fundamentally. However, even today, after almost a century of quantum mechanics being formulated, the interpretation of quantum mechanics remains a matter of intense debate. Some physicists choose to ignore the problem of interpretation altogether, preferring to work on the practical applications.

In the early days of quantum mechanics, Werner Heisenberg formulated quantum mechanics by making extensive use of abstract mathematics, a formulation that is known as matrix mechanics. Schrödinger chose to formulate quantum mechanics in a manner that he thought was less abstract and more visually appealing. Inspired by de Broglie's wave-particle duality, Schrödinger developed what is known as wave mechanics, an alternate formulation of quantum mechanics. Both matrix mechanics and wave mechanics are equivalent; they predict the same results. This is expected, since regardless of how we choose to formulate our theory, the physics describing real systems must remain the same. It is still extremely important to rigorously show that two different formulations of a theory are equivalent, and understand their differences and how they still paint the same physical picture.

Physics earnestly began with Isaac Newton's mechanics, where force plays a central role. However, for more complex systems, it is not possible to directly determine all the forces acting on the body, and Newton's laws cannot be straightforwardly applied. This is where the Lagrangian and Hamiltonian formulations become important. The Lagrangian formulation is an alternate formulation of classical mechanics, where the action plays the central role, instead of force. The action is the time integral of the Lagrange, which is the difference between the kinetic and potential energies of the system. The action is a fundamental parameter, since all physical systems have been found to move in a way that minimizes the action. The Hamiltonian formulation is also based on energy, and not force. The Hamiltonian is equal to the total energy (the sum of kinetic and potential energies) for a conservative system (systems for which the potential energy does not vary with time).

The Hamiltonian plays a central role in Schrödinger's quantum mechanics. Schrödinger equation is essentially an eigenvalue equation, and the eigenvalue that comes from solving the equation is the total energy of the system (which is the Hamiltonian for conservative systems).

We have seen that Schrödinger equation in one dimension is:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + V\psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}$$

The equation can also be written in this form:

$$\hat{H}\psi = E\psi$$

where \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian operator:

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + V$$

This is a quantum operator, which is represented by a Hermitian matrix. If we multiply this matrix with the wave function of the system ψ , we get an eigenvalue E , which is the total energy of the system (provided the system is conservative). In the expression of the Hamiltonian operator, the first term accounts for the system's kinetic energy, and the second term accounts for the potential energy. A central problem in canonical quantum mechanics is solving Schrödinger equation for a system (for example, the hydrogen atom) and calculating the allowed energy levels.

However, as discussed before, Schrödinger equation does not account for relativistic behavior, and thus, cannot be applied for particles moving at very high velocities. Feynman's path integral formulation of quantum mechanics surpasses Schrödinger's quantum mechanics in usefulness when it comes to relativistic quantum mechanics and quantum field theory. The Schrödinger picture of quantum mechanics is based on the Hamiltonian, whereas as we have seen, the Lagrangian plays a central role in the path integral formulation.

In this project, we have developed a deep understanding of path integrals at an elementary level. We have also explored the conceptual difference between the propagator and the wave function mathematically as well as visually. Throughout the project, we have established the parallels between the path integral and canonical formulations of quantum mechanics, deriving many standard results of canonical quantum mechanics using path integrals. This not only strengthens conceptual understanding of quantum mechanics, but also allows a proper appreciation of the equivalence between different mathematical formulations of the same physical theory. In the future, this knowledge may be used to understand how path integrals are used in quantum field theory, study the interactions between elementary particles using Feynman diagrams and study perturbation theory and scattering phenomena using the free particle propagator, among other things.

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APPENDIX 1: GAUSSIAN INTEGRALS

The Gaussian function is one of the most important mathematical functions, mainly because it describes a wide range of natural phenomena, and also because of its mathematical simplicity, making it easier to deal with. The Gaussian function is of the form:

$$f(x) = e^{-x^2}$$

If we plot this function $f(x)$ as a function of x , the area under the curve from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$ is $\sqrt{\pi}$. Since the integration of a function over the independent variable gives the area under the curve of the function plotted as a function of that independent variable, we have:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}$$

This result can also be mathematically obtained using the properties of gamma function.

Let us generate a plot of $f(x) = e^{-x^2}$ as a function of x using Python. The code and the output are shown below:

```
from pylab import *
x = linspace(-5,5,100000000)
y = exp(-x**2)
ylim(0,1.1)
title("Gaussian function")
xlabel(r'x', size=15)
ylabel(r'f(x)', size=15)
plot(x,y,'g-',label='Gaussian function',lw=2)
legend(loc='best')
grid()
show()
```


Now, we will evaluate the integral:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx$$

Let us introduce a new variable $u = x/\sqrt{2}\sigma$. The limits of the integration will again not be affected by this change in variable. This implies $du = dx/\sqrt{2}\sigma$, or $dx = \sqrt{2}\sigma du$.

Thus, in terms of u , we can write:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx = \sqrt{2}\sigma \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-u^2} du = \sqrt{2}\sigma\sqrt{\pi} = \sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$$

The parameter σ determines the width of the Gaussian function: a large value of σ corresponds to a Gaussian function that is more spread out and wide; a small value of σ corresponds to a narrower Gaussian function. This has been illustrated below. We have plotted the function $f_1(x) = e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2}$ for $\sigma = 1$ and $\sigma = 5$. The narrow green curve corresponds to the smaller value of σ ($\sigma = 1$), and the blue curve, which is more wide and spread out, corresponds to the higher value of σ ($\sigma = 5$).

```
from pylab import *
x = linspace(-15,15,100000)
sigma1 = 1
sigma2 = 5
y1 = exp(-x**2/(2*(sigma1**2)))
y2 = exp(-x**2/(2*(sigma2**2)))
ylim(0,2)
title("Plots of f1(x) as a function of x for small and large  $\sigma$ ")
xlabel(r'x', size=15)
ylabel(r'f1(x)', size=15)
plot(x,y1,'g-',label='small value of  $\sigma$ ',lw=2)
plot(x,y2,'b-',label='large value of  $\sigma$ ',lw=2)
legend(loc='best')
grid()
show()
```


Now, let us consider the integral:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx$$

Let us again introduce a new variable $v = x - a$. The limits of the integration will not be affected by this change in variable. Also, in this case, $dv = dx$. Thus, we can write:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{v^2}{2\sigma^2}} dv$$

Using the previous result $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx = \sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$, we get:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{v^2}{2\sigma^2}} dv = \sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$$

Now, let us divide both sides of the equation $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx = \sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$ by $\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$. This gives us:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx = 1$$

Since the above integral amounts to 1, the Gaussian function $e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$ is said to be normalized when it is divided by the factor $\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$. The normalized Gaussian function is given by:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

Another important result regarding Gaussian integrals is:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-Ax^2+Bx} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{A}} e^{B^2/4A}$$

If we multiply both sides of the above equation by a constant e^C (C is a constant), we get:

$$e^C \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-Ax^2+Bx} dx = e^C \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{A}} e^{B^2/4A} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{A}} e^{B^2/4A+C}$$

This gives us another important result:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-Ax^2+Bx+C} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{A}} e^{B^2/4A+C}$$

We will now use this result to derive the expression of an integral which we have used in our derivation of the propagator. Let us start with the integral:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-k_1(x-a)^2 - k_2(x-b)^2} dx$$

The argument inside the exponential can be simplified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} -k_1(x-a)^2 - k_2(x-b)^2 &= -k_1x^2 - k_1a^2 + 2k_1xa - k_2x^2 - k_2b^2 + 2k_2xb \\ &= -(k_1+k_2)x^2 + 2(k_1a+k_2b)x - (k_1a^2+k_2b^2) \\ &= -Ax^2 + Bx + C \end{aligned}$$

where $A = k_1 + k_2$, $B = 2(k_1a + k_2b)$ and $C = -(k_1a^2 + k_2b^2)$.

Now, using the result $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-Ax^2+Bx+C} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{A}} e^{B^2/4A+C}$, we can proceed with the original integral as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-k_1(x-a)^2-k_2(x-b)^2} dx &= \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{k_1+k_2}} e^{\frac{4(k_1a+k_2b)^2}{4(k_1+k_2)}+(-k_1a^2-k_2b^2)} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{k_1+k_2}} e^{\frac{k_1^2a^2+k_2^2b^2+2k_1k_2ab-k_1^2a^2-k_2^2b^2-k_1k_2a^2-k_1k_2b^2}{(k_1+k_2)}} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{k_1+k_2}} e^{\frac{2k_1k_2ab-k_1k_2a^2-k_1k_2b^2}{(k_1+k_2)}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{k_1+k_2}} e^{-\frac{k_1k_2(a-b)^2}{k_1+k_2}} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we arrive at the result:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-k_1(x-a)^2-k_2(x-b)^2} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{k_1+k_2}} e^{-\frac{k_1k_2}{k_1+k_2}(a-b)^2}$$

Now, we will derive another result of Gaussian integrals that we have used in our derivation of Schrödinger equation for the free particle. Let us evaluate:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx$$

First, we define $\phi(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{ikx} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\phi}{dk^2} &= \frac{d^2}{dk^2} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{ikx} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx \right) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{d^2}{dk^2} e^{ikx} \right) e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (-x^2 e^{ikx}) e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we get:

$$\frac{d^2\phi}{dk^2} = - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (x^2 e^{ikx}) e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx$$

Now, let us evaluate the above expression at $k = 0$:

$$\frac{d^2\phi}{dk^2}_{k=0} = - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx$$

This is precisely the integral we started with.

We have already seen that:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-Ax^2+Bx} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{A}} e^{B^2/4A}$$

Putting $A = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2}$ and $B = ik$ in the above expression, we get:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2+ikx} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{ikx} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx = \phi(k)$$

Thus, we conclude:

$$\phi(k) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{A}} e^{B^2/4A}$$

Using $A = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2}$ and $B = ik$, we get:

$$\phi(k) = \sigma\sqrt{2\pi} e^{-\sigma^2 k^2/2}$$

Differentiating the above expression twice with respect to k , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\phi}{dk^2} &= \frac{d}{dk} \left[\sigma\sqrt{2\pi} \left(-k\sigma^2 e^{-\frac{\sigma^2 k^2}{2}} \right) \right] = -\sigma^3\sqrt{2\pi} \frac{d}{dk} \left(k e^{-\frac{\sigma^2 k^2}{2}} \right) \\ &= -\sigma^3\sqrt{2\pi} e^{-\sigma^2 k^2/2} + \sigma^5\sqrt{2\pi} k^2 e^{-\sigma^2 k^2/2} \\ &= \sigma^3\sqrt{2\pi} e^{-\sigma^2 k^2/2} [\sigma^2 k^2 - 1] \end{aligned}$$

Now:

$$\frac{d^2\phi}{dk^2}_{k=0} = -\sigma^3\sqrt{2\pi}$$

And previously we got:

$$\frac{d^2\phi}{dk^2}_{k=0} = - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx$$

Equating both the expressions for $\frac{d^2\phi}{dk^2}_{k=0}$, we arrive at:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx = \sigma^3\sqrt{2\pi}$$

Dividing both sides by $\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}$, we get:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} dx = \sigma^2$$

We have used this result when deriving Schrödinger equation for a free particle using the propagator.

APPENDIX 2: THE FREE PARTICLE PROPAGATOR AND PERTURBATION THEORY

Let us consider the familiar scenario: a particle moving from spacetime point **a** to spacetime point **b**. We can break this journey from **a** to **b** into two parts, by introducing an arbitrary intermediate spacetime point **c**. Then, according to the multiplicative law of propagators:

$$K(b, a) = \int dx_c K(b, c)K(c, a)$$

We initially fix the intermediate point **c** and sum over all paths from **a** to **c**, given by the Kernel $K(c, a)$, and then sum over all paths from **c** to **b**, given by the Kernel $K(b, c)$. Then we integrate over x_c to take into account all possible values of the intermediate point **c**. This final expression is nothing but the sum over all paths from **a** to **b**, given by $K(b, a)$.

The above equation is a logical result, and is valid both for free particles and particles with potential energies. Of course, if we are dealing with a particle that has a non-zero potential energy, we cannot use the free particle Kernel in the above expression; but the multiplicative law of propagators would still be valid.

Now, we have seen that finding the exact form of the Kernel for particles with potential energies is extremely complicated. In certain situation, we can use the free particle propagator in the above expression, even if the particle's potential energy does not remain zero at all times during the journey from **a** to **b**. This approach is a cornerstone of perturbation theory.

When dealing with complex systems, it often becomes unfeasible or impossible to obtain an exact solution. In such situations, we can start with a simplified version of the original system, for which the solution is known or can be obtained. We then introduce additional terms of increasing orders, known as correction terms, to this solution to account for the features of the original system that were ignored in the simplified picture. Essentially, we introduce small corrections or perturbations to this solution to obtain a solution that describes the original system with a reasonable degree of accuracy. This is what perturbation theory is basically about, and although this approach might appear messy, it is extremely useful in many areas of physics and mathematics.

Although a detailed discussion of perturbation theory is beyond the scope of this article, we will look at an interesting scenario to illustrate the basic idea. We aim to calculate the probability amplitude $K(b, a)$ of a particle going from point **a** to point **b**. We assume that initially the particle has no potential energy; it is free. This is the zeroth order approximation. In the zeroth order approximation, we may use the free particle propagators $K_0(b, c)$ and $K_0(c, a)$ in place of $K(b, c)$ and $K(c, a)$ in the expression $K(b, a) = \int dx_c K(b, c)K(c, a)$. This gives the total free particle propagator from **a** to **b**:

$$K_0(b, a) = \int dx_c K_0(b, c)K_0(c, a)$$

In the zeroth order approximation, we have $K(b, a) \rightarrow K_0(b, a)$. Now, let us assume that the particle momentarily experiences a non-zero potential at the intermediate point **c**, although it moves freely from **a** to **c**, and from **c** to **b**. This is the first order approximation. The propagator in the first order approximation is given by:

$$-\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{t_a}^{t_b} dt_c \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dx_c K_0(b, c) V(c) K_0(c, a)$$

Note that the above expression contains two integration variables (space and time), and we multiply the free particle propagators $K_0(b, c)$ and $K_0(c, a)$ with the potential at \mathbf{c} , $V(c)$.

Figure 14: The particle moves from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{c} freely, momentarily experiences a potential energy $V(c)$ at \mathbf{c} , due to which it is deflected from its original direction of motion, and then moves from \mathbf{c} to \mathbf{b} freely. (Source: *Path Integrals* by Andreas Wipf, slightly modified.)

We can extend this method further. In the second order approximation, the particle experiences a non-zero potential momentarily at two intermediate points \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{d} , where $t_d > t_c$ since the particle moves forward in time. The particle behaves like a free particle from \mathbf{a} to \mathbf{c} , \mathbf{c} to \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{d} to \mathbf{b} . In the expression for the propagator, we need to integrate with respect to the space and time variables for all the intermediate points (in this case, \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{d}).

Figure 15: In the second order approximation, the particle moves from a to c freely, momentarily experiences a potential energy $V(c)$ at c , moves from c to d freely, momentarily experiences a potential energy $V(d)$ at d , and finally moves from d to b freely. (Source: *Path Integrals* by Andreas Wipf, slightly modified.)

The higher the order of the approximation, more accurately we can describe a particle that has some potential energy, using the free particle propagator. A physical application of the above method is the scattering of electrons on hitting a thin metal foil, due to interaction with the metal atoms. It is often of interest to find the probabilities of finding electrons at specific angles with the original direction, after the scattering. The probability amplitude (or the propagator) can be calculated using the above method, and by taking the square of the modulus of the propagator, the probability of finding the electron at that particular angle can be calculated. The potential at the point of interaction between the electron and the metal atoms is the electron's Coulombic potential energy when it is in the vicinity of the metal atom.

APPENDIX 3: BEYOND QUANTUM MECHANICS

Today, we have come a long way down the path that Newton and his contemporaries have laid down for us. We have gained a satisfactory understanding of a wide range of phenomena around us. However, when we zoom in and focus on the most fundamental aspects of the universe, physics has no satisfactory answer to offer us yet. There are five major problems in theoretical physics that remain unsolved, as outlined by Lee Smolin in his book *The Trouble With Physics*. First, the unification of the four forces and second, the reconciliation of general relativity and quantum mechanics. These two problems are perhaps interdependent: to solve one we need to solve the other. The third problem concerns the Standard Model, which is a theoretical framework based on quantum field theory that is used to study the physics of elementary particles. Although the Standard Model has made many correct predictions that have been experimentally verified, it has a lot of arbitrary parameters, and cannot explain certain puzzling phenomena like neutrino oscillations and baryon asymmetry. The fourth problem is understanding dark matter and dark energy, and the last problem is making sense of quantum mechanics, which is referred to as the quantum measurement problem. This is essentially the problem of interpretation of quantum mechanics. Many physicists, however, believe that this last problem is not a scientific problem in the first place, and should be best left to philosophers.

Let us think about the progress in the field of physics in the early 20th century and the early 21st century. In 1900, physicists were scratching their heads over blackbody radiation and ether. By 1925, we had discovered the general theory of relativity and much of quantum mechanics. In comparison, there has been no significant progress in fundamental physics between 2000 and 2025. Of course, overall we have made remarkable progress; for instance, advances in Artificial Intelligence and the discovery of the Higgs boson. However, we have been unable to gain any fundamentally new insight in theoretical physics. The major problems in theoretical physics we discussed have proved to be much more difficult to solve than physicists initially imagined. A single and consistent theory that solves all these problems is what can be referred to as a theory of everything. It's simply a theory that would explain all possible interactions in the universe in a single theoretical framework.

There are many different forces at play in the universe, but often many forces are just different forms of the same fundamental force. Over the years, physicists have come to the conclusion that there are four fundamental forces: the gravitational force, the electromagnetic force, the weak nuclear force and the strong nuclear force. Gravity here is the odd one out, because all the other forces can be explained in terms of exchange of certain fundamental particles called bosons, within the framework of quantum field theory. But we do not know for sure whether such a particle for gravity exists. Gravity is best understood as a consequence of the curvature of spacetime, as described by the general theory of relativity. Einstein, in his theory of relativity, proposed that matter and energy are basically the same thing, and so are space and time. The presence of matter/energy can curve the spacetime around it, and this curvature of spacetime affects the movement of the bodies present around. In this view, two bodies are not exactly pulling each other. They are moving toward each other due to the curvature of spacetime. Although general relativity has survived many experimental tests, it breaks down in extreme conditions (for instance, inside a black hole or at the Big Bang). This means general relativity is not a complete theory, and there could be a deeper, all-encompassing theory which would account for dark matter, dark energy (etc.) naturally, unlike general relativity.

When Einstein was busy fighting his battle in the thickets of spacetime, other physicists were developing a new and revolutionary theory: quantum mechanics. Einstein himself also played an important role in the development of quantum mechanics, although he later refused to accept quantum

mechanics as a complete theory. Quantum theory was born when Planck showed that energy cannot radiate continuously, but only in discrete packets called quanta. This was an essential step in resolving the ultraviolet catastrophe, a mismatch between the predictions of classical physics and experimental observation for a blackbody. Planck showed that the energy is directly proportional to the frequency of emitted radiation, and thus is equal to a constant multiplied with the frequency (this constant is known as Planck's constant). It was Einstein's insight that to explain the photoelectric effect, we must think of light as a stream of discrete quanta (called photons) as well. Einstein argued that light must be thought of as having a particle nature, contrary to the classically established wave theory of light. Today, we say that light has dual nature: the wave theory explains some phenomena while you need the particle theory to explain some other phenomena. This sparked de Broglie's great idea that just like light (supposed to be a wave) has dual nature, matter (supposed to be of particle nature) has a wave nature too. This idea has been verified by studying the diffraction pattern of electrons, and has wide ranging practical applications, like the electron microscope. The next big step in the quantum revolution came with Heisenberg showing that it is impossible to determine both the position and momentum of a particle simultaneously. This is the famous uncertainty principle. This uncertainty in quantum mechanical measurements is not due to limitations of our measuring device; it is an inherent feature of the universe. The uncertainty principle introduced an element of randomness in quantum mechanics, and some prominent physicists, including Einstein, were not comfortable with this.

The canonical formulation of quantum mechanics was complete once Schrödinger gave his equation, and Max Born interpreted the wave function in Schrödinger equation as a probability amplitude, the square of the modulus of which would give us the corresponding probability. However, quantum mechanics still remained extremely counterintuitive, causing many physicists to question its completeness. Quantum mechanics reduced everything to probability. According to quantum mechanics, we can no longer determine exact properties of a particle, like its position or momentum. We can only calculate the possible values of the properties and the probability of each possibility. Some physicists accepted this radical shift in worldview, while others were not so happy about this.

Quantum field theory explains all the three fundamental forces of Nature, except gravity, by building on the principles of quantum mechanics. These three forces are all caused by the exchange of fundamental particles called bosons. There are two types of fundamental particles: bosons, which give rise to forces, and fermions, which make up the matter. After Einstein put forward his geometrical interpretation of gravity in his general theory of relativity, he, along with many other scientists, started looking for a geometric interpretation of electromagnetism. The weak nuclear and strong nuclear forces were not known back then. It was soon discovered, by Theodor Kaluza (and his theory was later improved by Oskar Klein), that the existence of an extra, hidden dimension can account for electromagnetism in a world which is consistent with Einstein's general relativity. In other words, Kaluza "applied Einstein's general theory of relativity to a five-dimensional world and found electromagnetism," as Lee Smolin writes in *The Trouble With Physics*. But why do not we see this extra dimension? A possible reason could be that these dimensions are curled up to very small lengths and we cannot perceive them. These dimensions are so small that even elementary particles are not able to enter these dimensions.

String theory, probably the best candidate for a theory of everything, takes the idea of unifying forces by adding extra dimensions to new heights. The most advanced version of string theory, M theory, is an eleven-dimensional theory. If string theory turns out to be correct, then the correct question about the final theory should be asked in terms of strings. String theory proposes that one dimensional "strings," the different modes of vibrations on which correspond to the different particles, are the most

fundamental building blocks of the universe, and no particle is any more fundamental than any other particle. In string theory, forces arise from the joining and breaking of strings. All forces and particles can be explained by assuming strings propagate in a fixed background in such a way so as to minimize the area taken up. String theory basically replaces the idea of zero-dimensional point particles with the idea of a one-dimensional string of energy. Interestingly, string theory was initially developed as a theory of the strong nuclear interaction. But then it was discovered that string theory includes all the three forces plus gravity. The latter, as a requirement, must be included for the theory to work. This indicated that instead of just describing the strong nuclear interaction, string theory is in fact the theory that unifies all the four forces of Nature. But string theory made an outlandish claim: the universe has much more than just four dimensions, and the “extra” dimensions are curled up to extremely small lengths. Although string theory was found to be finite and consistent, many problems made it difficult for string theory to be established as the theory of everything. An important problem is that many different versions of string theory were discovered, all equally valid. Physicists believe that all these versions are different manifestations of some deeper, underlying theory, dubbed “M theory,” although all the details of this theory have not been completely worked out. There is one more problem with string theory: it is originally background dependent. We describe strings moving in a fixed background, in fixed space and time. Quantum field theory is background dependent as well. But general relativity is background independent. And ideally, we would expect a final theory to be background independent too. This means, the properties of the background (spacetime) should be derivable from the equations of the theory, and we must not fix the properties of the background and increase the number of inputs of the theory.

There are alternatives to string theory, the best alternative being loop quantum gravity which attempts to apply the principles of quantum mechanics to gravity. General relativity, as we know, describes gravity as a consequence of the curved geometry of spacetime. Loop quantum gravity, however, suggests that space itself is discrete and granular (not continuous). Also, loop quantum gravity can be formulated independent of the background independent. Loop quantum gravity assumes that space is emergent from discrete building blocks.

The problem with string theory and loop quantum gravity is that they are not well understood even today, and they make no prediction that can be easily tested experimentally. String theory has made no unique and viable prediction. The predictions of string theory, if proved to be true, will not conclusively prove that string theory is true. And even if these predictions are false, string theory might still be true. While string theory and loop quantum gravity are undoubtedly promising and elegant theories, it is important to remain sceptical until we have enough experimental evidence. After all, science is about the real world. Beautiful theories need not be true. Working on theoretical physics today is more likely to generate new insights in abstract mathematics rather than any insight about the physical world. It can no longer be said that theory and experiment go hand-in-hand, like it was during the early 20th century. This has led many prominent physicists to conclude that physics is currently “lost in math,” and we should take physics back to its empirical roots. However, it may not always be a bad thing if exploring physics takes us to the land of mathematics, because mathematics is the most fundamental level of understanding that we know of. Mathematical insights might find their use in some physical theory sooner or later. Because mathematics has it all, and studying mathematics could be a “short-cut” to understanding the fundamental structure of the physical universe, without having to rely on any messy experimental methods or data.

It is surprising how many abstract mathematical concepts, years after they were developed, turned out to provide the perfect theoretical framework needed to describe various aspects of the physical world.

Even though many of us believe mathematics is a human invention, it is almost as if the world was created using mathematics. Eugene Wigner called this the “unreasonable effectiveness of mathematics.” When linear algebra and the concepts of vector spaces, matrices etc. were developed so many years back, nobody at that time could think of any direct applications of these ideas in explaining the physical world. (Solving a set of linear equations for a real-life problem – like the ones we used to do back in high-school – is not really an application in understanding the physical world). But now we know that the entire formulation of quantum mechanics is based on a certain type of vector space, and eigenvalues and matrices offer us a well-defined mathematical way of predicting the possibilities and probabilities corresponding to measurements we make on a system in quantum mechanics. Beyond that, quantum mechanics has led us to quantum field theory and the Standard Model of particle physics, where to explain interactions between particles, we make extensive use of the mathematics of symmetry groups, which was, again, developed many years back without any application in mind. Although Max Tegmark’s “mathematical universe” hypothesis sounds crazy to many, all of this could be suggestive of the fact that probably everything in the physical world has a mathematical description. Tegmark takes the argument further: the universe is not just described by mathematics; the universe *is* mathematics!

According to Platonism, mathematics is not invented by humans; we are only discovering the mathematical truths, but they have always been there and will always be there, regardless of whether the physical universe exists or not. The physical universe could be a manifestation of some subspace of the most general mathematical space possible, and everything in the physical universe probably has a unique counterpart in this mathematical subspace. Even better, this correspondence could be one-to-one, meaning to every object in the physical universe, there exists a unique corresponding object in the subspace. A mathematical space simply refers to a set of mathematical objects that follow certain mathematical rules among themselves. These objects are not physical objects; they could be abstract mathematical structures which cannot be perceived by our senses. In other words, we can only see them in the equations we write. So, every physical phenomenon could have a mathematical description, and if that is true, then once we find the mathematics behind all physical phenomena, we probably will be able to better appreciate the fundamental structure of the universe and formulate a “theory of everything.”

Now, let us discuss a specific point where mathematics could potentially directly help physics: explaining the emergence of spacetime. Since general relativity and quantum field theory seem to work with fundamentally incompatible descriptions of spacetime, many physicists speculate that spacetime is not fundamental, rather it is emergent from a deeper level of understanding. It is possible that this “deeper level” has no physical description at all, because it cannot contain within it the notions of “space” and “time” (since spacetime is emergent *from* this level). It is likely that underneath the spacetime description we are familiar with, there exists a deeper and entirely mathematical description of the universe, with no physical constraints. However, revealing this underlying mathematical structure, assuming it exists, would be no easy feat. We must keep in mind that it must not contain any concept of space or time within it; we must explain how the physical world around us emerges from this structure. In particular, explaining the emergence of time would be challenging. Everything in the physical universe changes with time, but a mathematical space does not change in its entirety. In other words, its constituents and the relations or mathematical rules they follow do not change. We need to explain how this “illusion” of change, and hence the illusion of time, emerges when we focus on a part of the entire mathematical structure, the part which is the physical world.

So when we move beyond spacetime and to the most fundamental level of understanding, we probably will not find “time” or “space” there. Whatever we will find there can probably be best described in the framework of information rather than in the framework of physical concepts like distance and time. A big question here is whether it is possible for the human mind, with all its limitations, to ever achieve such a fundamental level of understanding. But the best we can do is see how far mathematics can take us.

Let us look at a second example of how mathematics might accelerate the progress in theoretical physics. As anyone with even the slightest idea of the incompatibility of general relativity and quantum field theory knows only too well, it is possible that we perceive the existence of some phenomenon in the physical world, or some aspect of a theory describing the physical world, which seems to violate some other theory describing some other aspect of the physical world. Now, it could be the case that this apparent “problem” would vanish if we shift to a more fundamental level of understanding, which can probably be achieved by mathematics. Mathematics is much more general than physics in the sense that it deals with the space of all objects and structures (which are following certain mathematical relations between them), and it does not exclude any possibility. Physics, on the other hand, is only concerned about those possibilities that occur in the physical world. This means by studying physics we can only see a part of the whole, and the “problems” that arise when studying just this part might be automatically resolved if we look at the whole (mathematics). A simple illustration could be the fact that open systems like living organisms decrease entropy locally, and if you do not take the surroundings into account (the whole) and focus just on the system (a part of the whole), it may seem that entropy is decreasing and the second law of thermodynamics is violated. However, the overall entropy of the universe, as we know, always increases. Although it is not yet clear how to use this reasoning to solve the problems that arise when we attempt to reconcile gravity with quantum theory, the same approach (coupled with some good mathematics) might do the trick.

In conclusion, the key to unlocking the secrets of the universe might not lie in devising better experiments and formulating theories based on the results of these experiments. This approach has been remarkably successful in past, but it may be speculated that the future of physics might belong to mathematics – the only place where truth and beauty mean the same!